

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

Regional Bioeconomy Platform Success Stories Identification

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.6: Regional Bioeconomy Platform Success Stories Identification concerns the reporting on the Task 2.4: Identification of Success Stories in each Regional Bioeconomy Platform (RBP). This report includes the guidelines for completing the task as well as the 20 identified success stories, including their description, a milestones timeline of their innovation, and an analysis of their success based on the success criteria identified in Task 2.3 and reported on Deliverable 2.5.

The Guidelines were prepared by incommon and were followed by RBP leaders who coordinated the project partners of their RBP in their efforts to identify the necessary success stories. The identified success stories are progressively being uploaded on the BioRural toolkit and are now part of the ERBN, BioRural's rural bioeconomy network, contributing to and furthering the goals of the project.

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1 Introduction

For the purposes of Task 2.4: Identification of Success Stories in each Regional Bioeconomy Platform (RBP), BioRural partners need to identify bio-based solutions across Europe and across the five bio-economy themes that constitute 'success stories'.

The KPI is to identify at least 20 success stories in total, 5 per RBP covering all themes of the bioeconomy, i.e. 1 success story / bio-economy theme / RBP. New success stories will be continuously invited to increase the pool of best practice examples.

In order to facilitate the process, the consortium, led by incommon (task leader), developed guidelines for the criteria of what constitutes a success story based on the 8 success stories of the project and for the identification of these additional success stories. As the expected outcome of the task is to keep identifying more success stories, the second batch of these success stories will be reported at the end of the project, in the updated Deliverable (D2.7), and will continuously be added to the toolkit.

After their identification, success stories will be invited to join the ERBN and act as flagships of their respective RBPs. They will be invited to participate in the regional workshops, to announce their activities in the BioRural Toolkit and to help in the development of business plans.

It is noted that activities under Task 2.4 are being carried out successfully and the partnership is already close to meeting the KPI set for the end of Task 2.4 (M36). Specifically, in the framework of D2.6 (M24), the partnership has already identified 20 success stories and 3 out of 4 RBP have already identified 1 success story / bio-economy theme.

1.1 Methodology

The methodology for completing the task successfully included the following steps:

1. Introduce partners to the task during the first TPM and create a shared register (excel file) for inputting bio-based solutions that they come across at any stage of the project and could potentially constitute 'success stories' for this task
2. Produce Guidelines for the completion of the task, including on the identification and evaluation of success stories
3. Produce Reporting Templates for the homogenous reporting of success stories
4. Set a timeline to be followed by RBP leaders, with reporting milestones along the way
5. Monitor progress via a shared folder created on Google Drive where partners upload their templates and update an excel spreadsheet for tracking progress
6. Upload identified success stories on the BioRural Toolkit

1.2 Criteria for Success Stories

The bio-based solutions need to fulfill certain criteria, in order to constitute 'success stories'. These criteria have been identified at Task 2.3, which analysed the innovation processes of the 8 success stories that were initially part of the project, and were presented in Deliverable 2.5 prepared by Valorial.

The elements from Deliverable 2.5 upon which the criteria for success, applicable to this task (Task 2.4), have been based are summarised below:

- The transition to a circular bioeconomy in Europe is reliant on regional expertise that is balanced between traditional knowledge and innovative attempts.
- There is close collaboration with community stakeholders.

- The transition to sustainable rural development and its scaling up, in terms of circular and biobased initiatives, requires research and the testing of pilot schemes.
- Initiatives that flourish tend to be faithfully linked to their value chain and the handling of raw materials.
- Local resource management plays an integral part in the design of bioeconomy initiatives, as initial ideas are grounded and developed in line with regional needs and opportunities.

The above points are categorised in the graph below, retrieved from Deliverable 2.5.

Figure 1: Success stories noteworthy elements - BIORURAL

Based on these elements, the criteria for success for Task 2.4 were identified. The criteria will guide the identification of bio-based solutions and their evaluation as to whether they constitute success stories.

Primarily, the identified solutions need to be **rural, small-scale, circular** and **innovative**, as this profile is a prerequisite for the success stories of BioRural in general. Following this, they need to exhibit the following attributes:

- **Local-ness** of resources has been shown to be an important aspect, along with biomass management practices that are sustainable and genuine, enhancing overall **environmental sustainability**
- The **team** and the **network** behind the story play a crucial role in the success of the initiative, especially having an interdisciplinary background and skills as well as a **local stakeholder ecosystem**
- The **effectiveness** of the solution in answering the problem it seeks to solve tested through research, experimentation and **piloting**
- Its **relevance** and **applicability** to its context are significant in making a story successful, i.e. being aligned with relevant regional needs and opportunities.
- All success stories seem to have the capacity to **scale** and/or **replicate**, albeit at different levels depending on the specificities of each case
- **Financial sustainability** is necessarily an indicator of success
- Adding a more social dimension, which some success stories do possess, promoting **social cohesion**, is yet another aspect of success, whereby the community is benefited in some form or other.

2 Guidelines for identifying and reporting success stories

This section includes the guidelines developed by incommon for the Task for the smooth implementation of the activities. The guidelines were shared with RBP leaders and BioRural partners during M16 and included the following:

2.1 Process & Timeline for reporting on success stories

A Google Drive folder was set up for each RBP, including five templates, one for each bio-economy theme.

Partners could start from whichever theme was more convenient to them, depending on the success story that they were more familiar with. The same process will be followed to gather the second batch of success stories for Deliverable 2.7.

RBP leaders were encouraged to use the google sheet that had been created at the beginning of the project where all partners were invited to register any potential success stories they came across, exactly for the purposes of this Task. The file already included 25 potential success stories, from several RBPs and themes, so it was considered as a good place to start.

The progress on reporting was monitored on a regular basis, and reminders were sent accordingly to RBPs, following the timeline below, that was shared via the guidelines:

Activity	15 DEC 23	15 JAN 23	15 FEB 24	15 MAR 24	15 APRIL 24	31 MAY 24
Partners are familiar with Template	M16					
At least 1 success story / RBP		M17				
At least 2 success stories / RBP			M18			
At least 3 success stories / RBP				M19		
At least 4 success stories / RBP					M20	
At least 5 success stories / RBP						M21

Table 1: Timeline for reporting on first batch for D2.6

Activity	31 AUG 24	15 OCT 24	15 DEC 24	15 FEB 25	31 MAR 25
At least 1 success story / RBP	M24				
At least 2 success stories / RBP		M26			
At least 3 success stories / RBP			M28		
4 success stories / RBP				M30	
5 success stories / RBP					M31

Table 2: Timeline for reporting on second batch for D2.7

It was clearly stated that it was the responsibility of the RBP leaders to submit these templates on time.

2.2 Explanatory Tables

The tables of the Reporting Template, which partners needed to fill out for every success story they identified, were presented in the guidelines and they were filled out with the explanations of what kind of information was requested in every row.

It was noted that all text boxes were there to be filled out and that they could be filled out freely. As it was explained, partners could either fill in the tables with more information than requested or leave empty rows that were considered as not relevant with a particular success story, according to the specific aspects of each success story that was identified.

General Information	
Success Story Title	commercial name of bio-based solution
Subtitle - tagline	usually this is explanatory / descriptive of the main activity
Bioeconomy theme	you can choose one or more applicable themes
Core Activities	the main activities that the success story performs, could be one or more
Full Address	So that we can pinpoint them on the toolkit map
No of employees	including both full time and part time
Funding sources	including self-sustainable, national funding, private funding, loans, etc

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	2-3 sentences briefly giving an overview of the success story
Detailed Description	This is the space to write the narrative behind the story. Indicatively, it should include the problems that the solution seeks to solve, what it actually does, the way they embrace/integrate circularity and innovation* , the unique selling point, the social/ environment /economic impact, etc
The team behind the story	Not the names of the people but their capacities / qualities / backgrounds - essentially we want to know what kind of people are necessary for this kind of solution to be successful
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	Who is the market for the product / service / industry? Key clients refers to the actual clients and it can either be a client category or specific client(s) if this is more relevant. Key partners refers to any necessary partners for the initiative to exist.
Vision and Future plans	Where do they want to see themselves in a few years from now, what are their future plans, scale up, replication, automation, etc

***this is an integral part of BioRural - so, as we are looking only for cases that are both circular and innovative, we need to emphasise and describe these aspects.**

Milestones Timeline		
	Date or Year	Milestone
1		The team/innovators behind the success story will have to choose the 6 main things that happened to bring them where they are today, the turning points.
2		These can be things that happened internally - for instance, person A and B met and this was the beginning of it all
3		It can be external things that happened to the team - such as receiving a funding, or buying a machine, or finding land, etc
4		Or it can be things that are completely external to the team - such as the price of gas rising, a 'natural' disaster, a new law, etc
5		
6		

Measuring Success		
Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation [explain your rating, describe activities that relate to indicator]
local-ness	[1-5]	How local is it in terms of its resources? Is there input/resource availability locally? Is the product/input managed sustainably?
team and network	[1-5]	Is there a strong team behind the story? Do they possess an interdisciplinary background and skills? Is there a local ecosystem of stakeholders relevant to the initiative?
effectiveness - relevance - applicability	[1-5]	how well does it answer the problem(s) it seeks to solve? Is it indeed necessary? How realistic is its application? Does it provide something useful / necessary to society/economy/environment?
Testing & piloting - scalability & replicability	[1-5]	Was there a research, experimentation and piloting stage? Was that important to the success of the initiative? Is there more testing going on at later stages? Now? Is it realistically scalable and/or replicable? How easy is it to replicate in other areas of rural Europe?
financial sustainability	[1-5]	This can probably only really be answered by the people of the story.
social cohesion	[1-5]	Does it bring any positive value for the community, in any form? Does it create problems for the community?

Based on these Guidelines, RBP leaders coordinated the identification and evaluation of success stories in their respective RBPs and with their member-partners, and reported on them using the above Reporting Template.

The following sections present all 20 identified success stories, as these were reported by the partners of the project.

3 Identified Success Stories: North-West RBP

The section presents the identified success stories of the North West RBP, including the Netherlands, France, Germany and Denmark and represented in the project by DELPHY, VALORIAL, NP, IZES and AU. The identification process is ongoing and 2 out of 5 success stories have been selected, i.e. one success story under the “Food and Agriculture” bioeconomy theme and one success story under the “Biomaterials and Bioproducts” bioeconomy theme.

3.1 Bioeconomy Theme: Food & Agriculture

3.1.1 Green protein to replace soya in feed

3.1.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Green protein to replace soya in feed
Subtitle - tagline	Biorefining plant on Ausumgaard produce protein feed from grass
Bioeconomy theme	Food & Agriculture
Core Activities	<p>Full-scale biorefining plant on the Danish farm Ausumgaard produces green protein, which is used to replace soy in feed for monogastric animals - pigs and poultry. Green protein is a protein extracted from grass by biorefining with the aim of using it as a feed ingredient. The green protein has an amino acid composition that makes it particularly suitable for one-stomached animals, and it can therefore be used instead of imported soy.</p> <p>Several varieties of both grass and alfalfa are grown and used in the plant. The varieties are adapted to the soil conditions individually so that an optimal yield and protein content can be achieved. As grass is a sensitive crop, traffic in the field takes place in fixed trials. Up to 7 sleds of grass are taken per season.</p> <p>Main elements in production and biorefining at Ausumgaard</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Raw material (grass or alfalfa) 2. Receiving systems and pressing 3. Green fiber 4. Wet process 5. Green protein 6. Brown juice

General Information	
	Source: BioRefine
Full Address	Ausumgaard, Holstebrovej 101, 7560 Hjerm, Denmark
No of employees	20
Funding sources	GUDP = (Green Development and Demonstration Program) and Vestjyllands Andel

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	<p>The green biorefining technology is a process where fresh grass is separated into a fiber pulp, protein products and a residual liquid known as brown juice. The core product is the protein used for replacing soy in feed.</p> <p>At Ausumgaard they are growing grass on own-property and other farmers' fields for the protein production. Total nearly 300 organic grown hectares. Different crops - grass, clover, lucerne, alfalfa, after crops, and other bio resources are processed and tested in the plant.</p> <p>The plant is flexible and is continuously optimised and innovated.</p>
Detailed Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The grass is harvested directly and driven into the plant. It is important that the grass is processed within 6 – 8 hours. If it takes longer, the quality of the grass deteriorates sharply and the amount and quality of protein decreases. • On the grass protein plant, the liquid is squeezed out of the grass. As a result, green fiber comes out as a by-product. The green fiber has a dry matter percentage of approx. 40% and is mainly used for biogas. Trials are underway to investigate other possible uses, such as packaging, textiles and feed for cattle. • The liquid squeezed out of the grass is called green juice, and it is from here that the protein precipitates and separates in our carafe centrifuge. Inside the decanter centrifuge is a rotating device consisting of a cylindrical sphere with a built-in conveyor. The ball and the carrier rotate in the same direction, but not at the same speed. Since the protein has a higher density than the liquid, it settles on the inside of the ball, and in this way the protein and liquid are separated. • The separated liquid is called brown juice and has a dry matter percentage of about 5. The brown juice is mainly used for biogas plants, or it is directly spread on the field, but there could be other uses. • The separated protein now appears as a "paste" with approximately 50 percent dry matter content. This product must be dried to become stock fixed. After the drying, when the grass protein is suitable for long-term storage, the grass protein is put into big bags ready for storage or transport. The green protein can now be used for livestock feed.
The team behind the story	Ausumgaard, GUDP and Vestjyllands Andel
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>Farmers, Biogas plant for handling waste</p> <p>Key partners:</p> <p>Ausumgaard and Vestjyllands Andel</p>
Vision and Future plans	<p>Overall, it is the vision to implement the green protein concept as a part of a circular bioeconomy design in such a way that it eliminates outputs (waste and pollution) to a minimum and it seeks to use renewable resources, missing inputs, etc. (See the figure below)</p> <p>Concretely, innovative work is being done to increase the production of protein in rural areas based on local grown crops e.g. grass and alfalfa and thereby reduce import of soy.</p>

The Success Story Profile

Moreover, focus is on improving the quality of the protein so it can be used not only for animal feed but also for human nutrition as well.

The green protein concept (Morten Amby-Jensen, AU)

Milestones Timeline

	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2023	<p>The concept for a full Full-Scale biorefining plant for the production of green protein based on fresh grass demonstrated.</p> <p>Danish agriculture imports a lot of soy for animal feed, especially from South America. Now it is demonstrated that it is possible in a full scale plant to extract plant protein for use in feed by processing grass. This will be a huge step in the right direction if agriculture is to be able to source sustainable feed in the long term.</p> <p>Green biorefining can be the way to a green revolution in Danish agriculture.</p> <p>Grass is good for climate and environment compared to cereal crops as it reduces leaching of nutrients and increases carbon sequestration.</p> <p>Benefits from growing grass:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greater carbon sequestration in the soil than in cereal fields Greater flexibility in relation to drought and heavy rainfall because the grassland acts as a fungus Less pesticide uses on conventional farms because grass is rarely sprayed Less fertiliser application, as clover grass is self-sufficient in N Better economy in organic plant production, because clover grass, which is necessary for nitrogen supply, becomes a profitable crop Better utilisation of grass, which is grown for energy purposes in biogas plants Increased biodiversity, because grasslands are habitats for more animal and plant species than, for example, cereal fields
2	2024	Commercial production facility that sells green protein to livestock producers
3	2024	Concept for use of the fiber pulp in ruminant animal feed
4	2025	Optimised use of residual juice – brown juice - within biochemical, bioenergy and recycling of all nutrients.
5	2025	Fiber pulp used for high value lignocellulosic feedstock for biochemicals and biobased materials.
6	2026	Production of green protein in a quality that can be used in human food

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	4	The raw material- the grass – is grown locally and the biorefinery must be located in rural areas due to logistics and handling of grass and residuals.
team and network	5	A prerequisite for the concept to work is that several actors are involved. There must be cultivates of the biomass and there is a need for local disposals of both protein and the various residual streams from the plant.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	3	Raw material production, harvesting and logistics account for a significant share of the economy for green biorefining. In practice it might be difficult to achieve optimal conditions. The concept is very relevant, as it is not sustainable with the existing import of soy. The Ausumgaard plant has already documented the applicability of the concept.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	4	Technically, the facility and concept are scalable and can be copied elsewhere. However, there are certain conditions regarding producers and receivers of residual streams that must be present for the setup to work. It will not be the case in all rural areas.
financial sustainability	2	Focusing only on the production of protein feed, biorefining of grass is not financially sustainable. It is necessary to develop methods for utilizing the side streams from production to make the set-up financially sustainable, but it is already underway.
social cohesion	4	There is good social cohesion as the concept of biorefining of grass must be done locally and involves a large number of actors in a network that can strengthen the activity in rural areas.

Relevant links

1. <https://biorefine.dk/p/produktion>
2. <https://ausumgaard.dk/>

3.1.1.2 Conclusion

This endeavour aspires to serve as a bio-based solution that applies an holistic approach to the production and operational schemes it is based on, towards circularity and sustainability. Specifically, the main scope is to produce sustainable and healthy feed by enabling local supply chains and resources and optimising the use of resources - e.g. via maximising the utilisation of residual streams.

3.2 Bioeconomy Theme: Biomaterials and Bioproducts

3.2.1 Production of willow-compost for replacing sphagnum

3.2.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Production of willow-compost for replacing of sphagnum
Subtitle - tagline	Willow for bioenergy, compost, and biomaterials
Bioeconomy theme	Forestry/Agriculture/Bioenergy/Biomaterials
Core Activities	<p>At Ny Vraa in Tylstrup, Northern part of Denmark, the first willow was planted in 1989 and today the farm has about 600 ha of Willow - own fields and leased fields. Today, in total, energy willow is grown on approx. 5000 hectares in Denmark.</p> <p>At Ny Vraa willow has been grown as part of the field management. In 2012, the entire farm was converted into organic farming and today the energy crop willow is grown in all of the farm's 230 hectares. In addition, leased areas are included. The company has about</p>

General Information

twenty employees. Willow chips, compost, biofilters for mini-wetlands and bedding materials for livestock are the main products from the willow.

Ny Vraa has more than ninety different willow clones in their production. All the produced willow are sold, either as cuttings for new plantations or as upgraded bioproducts. The market is primarily Denmark, but also exports to other countries occur. The company also provides consultancy services concerning establishment and growing of willow and finally Ny Vraa can be hired as contractor for the establishment of new willow plantations and harvest of willow.

Recently, a new product has been developed – willow compost. The organic willow-based compost can replace sphagnum in horticulture, green houses, and private gardens. The development and optimisation of the process has taken 8 years and been very costly for the company. This product has become very interesting as the use of sphagnum is harmful to the environment due to the release of fixed carbon as CO₂ into the atmosphere. Therefore, traditional sphagnum is phased out due to the environmental impact. The willow compost is a mix of willow chips, clover grass and other natural nutrient-rich herbs.

Willow can be grown on different soil types. It is a unique crop that tolerates flooding for shorter periods during the growing season and for longer periods outside the growing season, i.e. in the autumn and winter periods. Willow has a high growth rate, is economically attractive and possesses good environmental properties and can reduce leaching of nutrients to the environment. Soil types that ensure a good water supply are suitable. Coarse sandy soils in dry areas and without irrigation may be problematic, as the yields are strongly variable and may be very low. Note that there is a risk that roots from willow can block drain lines. When producing willow on wetland soils, one must be aware that it can cause problems: especially harvesting of the crop can be difficult, as harvesting must take place when the willow is without foliage. Special equipment such as the use of belt tractors and belt harvest machines may be necessary.

Growing willow – a perennial crop - has several positive environmental and climate effects compared to growing annual cereal crops. Leaching of nitrate from the root zone is significantly lower from a willow field than from a field with annual cereal crops. The pesticide consumption is also much lower. In addition, there will in general be a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by growing willow compared to annual crops, because biomass can substitute fossil fuels, and there will be a carbon build up in the soil and less emission of nitrous oxide.

Cultivation guidelines for willow

Year 1:

- Willow planting: In April/May, with a planter machine, 75 cm between the rows and 150 cm between the double rows. The distance between the plants in the rows is 74 cm. About 12.000 seedlings per hectare.
- Roller: For retaining soil moisture and protecting seedlings against drying out.
- Weed control: Mechanical by weed harrow, inter-row cultivator, row rototillers, or harrow. In non-organic systems, standard herbicides can be used.

Year 2:

- Fertilizing: 120 kg N, 15 kg P and 50 kg K/hectare.

General Information	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weed control: Mechanical by weed harrow, inter-row cultivator, row rototillers, or harrows. In non-organic systems, standard herbicides can be used. <p>Year 3 or 4: (depends on yields)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harvest: (winter season), Exact cutter and wagon. Material directly to the heating plant or storage. • Mulcher: After harvesting, clean cutting in 3 – 5 cm stubble height. • Fertilizing: 120 kg N, 15 kg P and 50 kg K/hectare. • Weed control: Mechanical by weed harrow, inter-row cultivator, row rototillers, or harrows. In non-organic systems, standard herbicides can be used. Chemical by spraying. (perhaps only spots) <p>Year 5 - 20</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harvest: Every 3-4 years depending on growth and end use (winter season), Exact cutter and wagon. Material directly to the heating plant or storage. • Mulcher: After harvesting, clean cutting in 3 – 5 cm stubble height. • Fertilizing: 120 kg N, 15 kg P and 50 kg K/hectare.
Full Address	NY VRAA, Gammel Vraavej 31, 9382 Tylstrup
No of employees	20
Funding sources	The willow-compost concept is privately funded by Ny Vraa. The farm has received a standard Organic Area Grant to convert and manage the farm's agricultural areas organically. The purpose of the grant is to increase the organic area in Denmark and thereby achieve a number of benefits for the environment and biodiversity. The subsidy has enabled the farm to maintain organic agricultural production on the farm's agricultural land and sell organically produced food.

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	Growing willow on own and other farmers' fields for energy, bioproducts and willow compost. Total about 600 organic grown hectares of willow.
Detailed Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Willow can be grown on different soil types, is a unique energy crop, has a high growth rate, is economically attractive and possesses good environmental properties that can reduce leaching of nutrient salts. • The willow is planted in rows, with a row spacing of 75 cm and 150 cm between the double rows. The distance between the plants in the rows is 75 cm. About 12,000 seedlings per hectare should be planted. • On clay soils, there is usually no need for the application of nitrogen in the year of planting. On lighter sandy soils, however, 30-50 kg of nitrogen may be required in July already in the first year. In subsequent years, fertilisation must take place in March/April. The N-standard for energy willow is 120 kg N/hectare as well as 15 kg P/hectare and 50 kg K/hectare. The norm applies only to willow grown for harvesting, and only up to and including the 4th plan period after planting or chopping. • The growth of the willow is significantly inhibited if weeds appear, especially in the first year after planting. An effective chemical and/or mechanical cleaning must therefore be conducted in the year of planting and the subsequent 1-2 years.

The Success Story Profile	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy willow is harvested in the winter season and therefore the crop is also suitable for seasonal leveling. Willow can be harvested as whole shoots with a whole shoot harvester. It is a machine that harvests the willow at the root at full length. The willow is transported for storage in large stacks, e.g., at the edge of the field. Whole shoots can be stored for an extended period with limited dry matter loss and fungal flora and used, for example, for energy. Chipping of the full shoots can take place immediately before or in connection with delivery to, for example, a heating plant or a combined heat and power plant. After storing whole shoots over the spring and summer months, the moisture content is often reduced to approx. 25-30%, thereby achieving a better transfer price per ton of dry matter. • The most commonly used system is a self-propelled forage harvester equipped with a cutting table, which is adapted for harvesting willow. Alternatively, harvesting can be done with a tractor-towed harvester. For both the self-propelled and the towed harvester, chipping occurs simultaneously with harvesting. This system is suitable when the chips can be delivered directly from the field for consumption in a CHP plant during the harvest season itself. Willow chips with a moisture content of 50 % should only be stored for a few weeks in a field stack. Within 2-4 weeks, the temperature will rise to 50-70 °C, and there will be an energy loss. When storing willow chips in a field stack for 5 months, a dry matter loss of 15-25% will typically occur. • Yields ranging from 8 to 10 tons of dry matter per hectare per year can be expected under good growing conditions, i.e., with thorough weed control, fertilisation and cultivation on a soil with a good water supply.
The team behind the story	NY VRA, other farmers, and RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME 2014-2022
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	Farmers Key partners: Horticulture, gardening
Vision and Future plans	<p>The organic willow compost can replace sphagnum in horticulture and in private gardens. The process has taken 8 years and been very costly. This has become remarkably interesting as the use of sphagnum is phased out due to the high carbon emissions. The willow compost is mixed with clover grass and other natural nutrient-rich herbs.</p> <p>The willow can also be delivered to local heating plants.</p> <p>Extracts, together with the company SALIXIN, are extracted for cosmetics and food products and exported to twenty-five countries. NY VRAA also markets willow fences and willow baskets.</p> <p>Today, willow is grown on approx. 5000 hectares in Denmark.</p>

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2012	The entire farm to organic farming to ensure a sustainable future for Machinery for the willow industry, compost for horticulture, willow chips for bedding, willow planting to secure drinking water quality, willow feed animals and wildlife, extract to cosmetic and food supplement.
2	2022	Commercial marketing and sale of growing substrate based on willow to replace sphagnum.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	4	The raw material- willow and clover grass – is grown locally and the compost piles will be in rural areas due to logistics and handling of the materials.
team and network	3	Several actors are involved. There must be local cultivates of the willow and there is a need for local disposals of the various residual streams.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	4	Raw material production, harvesting and logistics account for a significant share of the economy. In practice it might be difficult to achieve optimal conditions. The concept is very relevant, as it is not sustainable with the existing use of sphagnum. Ny Vraa have already documented the applicability of the concept.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	4	Technically, the facility and concept are scalable and can be copied elsewhere. However, there are certain conditions regarding growers of willow and receivers of residual streams that must be present for the setup to work.
financial sustainability	3	Today, it is 10-15 percent more expensive to produce willow compost compared to traditional sphagnum. In the future, a legal ban on digging up the traditional sphagnum from bogs can be expected, and this is expected to increase demand significantly
social cohesion	4	There is good social cohesion as the production will be done locally and involves several actors in a network that can strengthen the activity in rural areas.

Relevant links

1. <https://www.nyvraa.dk>
2. [PILE KOMPOST - spagnumfri og økologisk \(dyrk.dk\)](#)
3. <https://www.tv2nord.dk/aalborg/dit-spagnum-er-daarligt-for-miljoet-og-er-forbudt-i-england-nordjysk-virkosomhed-tager-kampen-op>

3.2.1.2 Conclusion

Ny VRA success story serves as a good paradigm not only thanks to the development of sustainable agricultural practices, meaning the investment on organic farming and on growing a crop with positive impacts to the surrounding environment, but also thanks to the willingness to continuously deliver new ideas and solutions, resulting in new products, such as the willow-compost which may substitute traditional materials and offer multiple environmental benefits.

4 Identified Success Stories: North-East RBP

The section presents the identified success stories of the North-East RBP, including Poland, Lithuania and Latvia and represented in the project by VDU, LBTU and IUNG. The North-East RBP have already reached the KPI, since they have identified one success story per bioeconomy theme, while they have identified three success stories falling within the “Biomaterials and Bioproducts” category.

4.1 Bioeconomy Theme: Food & Agriculture

4.1.1 Garlic Moon

4.1.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Garlic moon
Subtitle - tagline	High biological value food products and ingredients for functional nutrition
Bioeconomy theme	Food/agriculture systems
Core Activities	Production of black garlic by long fermentation and food supplements for functional nutrition
Full Address	Rūta st. 2, Pypliq village, Kaunas district, LT53456 https://www.juodascesnakas.lt/
No of employees	3 depends on the need
Funding sources	Private

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	<p>Garlic moon black garlic is made by naturally ripening and fermenting locally grown white garlic without the use of preservatives or chemical additives. Black garlic is produced by slow fermentation, without the use of plastic to retain moisture, and without the use of any chemical additives or preservatives, i.e. fermentation takes place completely naturally under the influence of humidity and temperature.</p> <p>For the production of black garlic, only local high-quality raw materials are used - garlic heads of the old Lithuanian variety, which are dug up and cleaned manually. The sorted garlic raw material, unsuitable for fermentation, is used by another small family farm for the production of food spices.</p> <p>Products and ingredients for functional nutrition are produced on the farm from the unsightly fraction of black garlic that is not suitable for sale.</p>
Detailed Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Black garlic "Garlic moon" is produced by long-term fermentation of locally grown white garlic of the old Lithuanian variety. Natural fermentation technology adapted to the local garlic variety by the scientists of the VDU Agricultural Academy is used in the production. ✓ Black garlic "Garlic moon" is produced using a long fermentation method. Black garlic is fermented for 50-60 days. The longer the fermentation, the higher the bioactive properties can be achieved. Meanwhile, a short fermentation produces a product of another black garlic. ✓ “Garlic moon” does not use plastic packaging in the garlic fermentation process. To preserve moisture, during normal fermentation, garlic is placed in a plastic vacuum, while “Garlic moon” uses a more complex fermentation technology to preserve moisture - humidity is regulated manually. This prevents microplastic particles in food.

The Success Story Profile	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ No chemical additives or preservatives are used, fermentation takes place completely naturally only thanks to humidity and temperature. ✓ Local high-quality raw material is used for fermentation, i.e. only garlic safely grown on Lithuanian farms is used, which is dug and cleaned manually so that it is not damaged and remains healthy. ✓ After fermentation, some of the black garlic does not look good. It is not put on the market but is used on the farm in the production of products and ingredients for functional nutrition. ✓ The sorted garlic raw material, unsuitable for fermentation, is used by another small family farm to produce food spices. <p>People in Asian countries (Thailand, South Korea, and Japan) have been cooking and using black garlic as a traditional food for centuries. Black garlic, which has appeared on the global market in the last few decades, has become a well-known functional food due to its wide range of biological functions, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, hyperlipidaemia and obesity-reducing, liver-restoring, and neuroprotective effects.</p> <p>Functional foods are considered foods that contribute to people's optimal nutrition, health status and quality of life, reducing the risk of disease and promoting the proper functioning of human organs and systems. Many extensive studies have been conducted on the biological activity and therapeutic benefits of black garlic, which only confirmed the knowledge of folk medicine about the therapeutic benefits of garlic since ancient times.</p> <p>Benefits of Black Garlic:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● easily digestible; ● twice as many antioxidants and natural antibiotics as in regular garlic; ● rich in potassium, magnesium, calcium, phosphorus, selenium, vitamin B6, vitamin C; ● strengthens immune function; ● lowers cholesterol; ● helps maintain a stable blood sugar level; ● improves digestion and reduces other stomach ailments; ● has a strong antiviral effect. <p>The uniqueness of black garlic is that it can be used very widely to flavor food, from desserts to meat dishes. Black garlic has a shelf life of up to a year, while dug white garlic is difficult to keep for up to half a year.</p> <p>“Garlic moon” production business was started by a businesswoman in a rural area. She created a workplace for herself and seasonal workers in the rural area. “Garlic moon” products are sold in the farm's online store and in physical stores of partners in Lithuanian cities.</p> <p>“Garlic moon” products aim to contribute to people's complete nutrition.</p> <p>“Garlic moon” black garlic is fermented from the local raw material of the old garlic variety, which encourages Lithuanian farmers to include old cotton varieties in crop rotations and increase biological diversity.</p>
The team behind the story	<p>The young businesswoman was interested in the research of the scientists of the Academy of Agriculture of VMU, who conducted experiments on the adaptation of natural fermentation of black garlic to local conditions and studied what good properties the local garlic variety acquires and maintains through long-term fermentation. The two-way</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>communication led to the transfer of the black garlic fermentation process from the research stage to business.</p> <p>After helping with the commercial production of black garlic, the young entrepreneur started communicating with another team of scientists from the Institute of Horticulture of Lithuanian Research Center for Agriculture and Forestry (LAMMC), taking different samples to determine which substances are formed at which stages of fermentation, in order to obtain the best black garlic that is fermented characteristics of the local garlic variety. A collaborative effort is being sought to find funding sources to initiate research.</p>
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>End users: Lithuanian residents, current production volumes are too small to meet the rapidly growing local demand. "Garlic moon" products reach end users through a private online store https://www.juodascenasnakas.lt/ and "Village to home" online store https://kaimasinamus.lt/ of the Public Agency of Agriculture, and food stores and pharmacies as well. The scale of production is already too small.</p> <p>Clients: partner food stores in Lithuanian cities ("Kaimo krautuvė", "Naminukas", "Krautuvėlė Kamara", "Maisto namukas", "Žalioji skrynja", "Skonio gama", etc.) and one of the oldest pharmacies "Valerijonas" in Northern Lithuania.</p>
Vision and Future plans	<p>The production vision of "Garlic moon" products is to offer consumers a wider range of high biological value food products and ingredients that would enrich their diet with biological substances valuable for health.</p> <p>New products from black garlic are being developed.</p> <p>The demand for "Garlic moon" products far outstrips sales, and expansion of production is under consideration.</p>

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2019-2020	Experimental study by scientists of the Academy of Agriculture of VMU – tests of fermentation of local varieties of garlic according to old Eastern technologies.
2	2020-2021	Cooperation with scientists of the Academy of Agriculture; the preparatory stage for the start of production (acquisition of equipment, installation of premises, search for suppliers of raw garlic), and search for sales channels.
3	2021	Start of black garlic production and first sales. Creation of the "Garlic moon" brand.
4	2022-2023	<p>An experimental study on the bioactive substances and quality of black garlic substances in different fermentation cycles. Cooperation with scientists of the Institute of Horticulture of Lithuanian Research Center for Agriculture and Forestry.</p> <p>Design, production and sales of new products from the unsightly form of black garlic.</p>

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	<p>Local participation: the adaptation of the old Lithuanian variety of garlic raw material allows the production of a unique local product; increasing demand for local raw materials; and jobs in the countryside are maintained.</p> <p>Strengthening the network of local producers and consumers: together with other local producers (within a radius of 10 km), hikes for consumers are organised, during which participants are introduced to the products of local producers and can buy them. The scrapped garlic raw material that is not suitable for fermentation is transferred to a local small family farm as an additive to produce food spices from vegetables grown on the farm.</p> <p>The uniqueness of local products: the created brand "Garlic moon" helps to understand the unique features of the food systems of the Lithuanian region.</p>
team and network	5	<p>Diverse experience: the black garlic producer is advised by a multidisciplinary team of scientists with different backgrounds and experiences, which is very important in solving the issues of improving the long-fermentation technology of local varieties of garlic and applying it to large-scale production; as well as determining the composition and quality characteristics of black garlic in different fermentation cycles.</p> <p>Local network of distributors: Part of the production is distributed through a private online store https://www.juodascesnakas.lt/ and "Village to home" online store https://kaimasinamus.lt/. The distributor network of the other part of Garlic moon production consists of shops focused on the sale of local food products (especially those that enrich complete functional nutrition), and in recent years, the oldest pharmacy in Lithuania.</p>
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	<p>Increasing the biological value of food: The biological value of food is constantly decreasing. The production of garlic moon products aims to create products of high biological value to enrich people's diet with biological substances valuable for health.</p> <p>Reduces food waste: The long-term fermentation of black garlic prolongs the use of garlic and reduces the generation of waste; unsightly fermentation product processed on the farm itself into products and ingredients for functional nutrition; and garlic raw material unsuitable for fermentation is used in the production of food spices on another farm.</p> <p>Conservation of Biodiversity: Encourages farmers to include local ancient garlic varieties in crop rotation.</p>
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	4	<p>Initial experimental research: First, technology experiments on the adaptation of natural fermentation of black garlic to local conditions were carried out. They encouraged the commercial production of black garlic by long fermentation from one of the raw materials of the old Lithuanian garlic variety.</p> <p>Ongoing Research: New Garlic moon products are being developed and their quality and biological value are being tested.</p> <p>Experimental research has begun: the first samples have been collected to examine the bioactive substances and quality characteristics of black garlic in different fermentation cycles. Funding sources are being sought to carry out laboratory research, as well as to expand the range of research.</p>

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
financial sustainability	5	Adaptation to local conditions: experimental studies on long-term fermentation of local raw garlic are needed.
social cohesion	5	High biological value products and ingredients for functional nutrition are produced, which enrich people's food with biological substances valuable for health. Local raw materials used in production encourage the involvement of producers and consumers in local food systems.

The success of the business relies on a holistic approach that considers global perspectives, local engagement, diverse expertise, environmental consciousness, strategic partnerships, financial sustainability, and responsiveness to evolving societal expectations in the agriculture and food industry.

4.1.1.2 Conclusion

“Garlic moon” serves as a great paradigm of bio-based solution in the food and agriculture sector, since it successfully achieves its main goal, i.e. provide sustainable nutrition products and ingredients of high quality, by incorporating all the desired characteristics of a success story: from the deployment of traditional practices upgraded via research and innovation, in order to produce high quality products and maximise resource efficiency, to the adoption of circularity to almost all production stages and the engagement/empowerment of local communities, through networking and awareness activities.

4.2 Bioeconomy Theme: Forestry

4.2.1 Wood waste processing company Druplat

4.2.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Wood waste processing company Druplat
Subtitle - tagline	Wood waste is a significant segment of waste to be processed
Bioeconomy theme	Forestry
Core Activities	Druplat is one of the leading companies in Latvia that processes various kinds of wood residues and wood waste. The company also chips various forest residues, as well as provides wood chip transport services and other services. The company does its business at four wood waste collection and storage sites (in Cesis, Sigulda and Tinuzi), as well as at the site of the customer.
Full Address	18 Radzu Street, Riga, LV - 1057, Latvia
No of employees	39
Funding sources	Own-financing, loans from legal and natural persons, financial leasing, EU co-funding

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	Druplat performs the following processing activities: crushing timber and various kinds of wood waste from logging, wood processing, manufacture of wooden products as well as packaging to produce wood chips (crushed secondary wood). By producing energy resources, Druplat reduces the pressure on the environment.
Detailed Description	In Latvia, various products of wood – furniture, boxes, wooden construction waste and other pieces of wood – are still simply burned by many individuals because they are not allowed to be used as fuel. To adapt wood to a specific use, it is treated with various chemicals; therefore, it is no longer considered to be pure wood. Some of the wood waste ends up in landfills or is simply dumped in forests or abandoned areas, thus degrading the surrounding environment. Druplat contributes to solving such problems by producing fuel

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>chips from sorted wood waste (crushed secondary wood), thus reducing the need for landfills and producing energy resources.</p> <p>First, the company separates and sorts recyclable wood waste that has been transported to its collection and storage sites, then the wood waste is fed into a crushing machine equipped with magnets to separate metals that the wood waste may contain. This allows the company to control the quality of wood chips and protect the machine from damage. The unusable wastes separated (e.g. metals and films) are collected in separate containers and transported to cooperation partners for further processing. After the wood waste has been crushed, it is transported either to veneer sheet and wood panel production company KRONOSPAN Riga Ltd (which produces chipboards from recycled wood chips) or to heating companies (wood chips are used as fuel). The crushed chemically treated wood waste, which is not suitable either as fuel for boiler houses or as an input for the production of a new product, is burned in specialised furnaces by companies having a permit to burn this kind of waste.</p> <p>Currently, the company works on engineering a technological process prototype and pilot equipment for processing wood and textile waste into an innovative product – wood chip blocks. This innovation can further contribute to both regional sustainability and the circular wood economy.</p>
The team behind the story	<p>The key to its success is the company’s reputation, business relations with sustainably-minded cooperation partners in the market of Latvia, employees, as well as executive board members having their strategic vision and long-term work experience in the field of waste management.</p>
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>The main suppliers of wood waste are retailers, packers, equipment importers, waste management companies, as well as private individuals.</p> <p>The main cooperation partners are Eko Energy Ltd (collection, processing and management of waste and secondary raw materials), KRONOSPAN Riga Ltd (veneer sheet and wood panel manufacturer), SCHWENK Latvija Ltd (manufacturer of building materials), as well as local heating companies, which use wood chips as fuel.</p>
Vision and Future plans	<p>Druplat has made significant investments in development – both in technical support and in employees. Therefore, the company plans to increase the output, as well as improve the wood waste processing process by introducing innovative processing and sorting technologies in the coming years.</p> <p>To achieve its objectives, Druplat as a cooperation partner participates in the EU LIFE integrated project Waste To Resources Latvia – Boosting Regional Sustainability and Circularity by Introducing the Concept of Using Waste as Resources (LIFE Waste To Resources IP) (2021-2028), activity Implementation of pilot projects for determining the end status of waste.</p> <p>The purpose of the pilot project is to produce new innovative building materials from various wood and textile wastes. During the implementation of the project activity, it is planned to install a trial production line that demonstrates the possibility of producing sawdust blocks from wood waste and adding textile waste as an additional input during the block production process. Such blocks are intended to be used in the production of wooden shipping pallets. The project activities also involve holding online seminars for waste management companies in other regions of Latvia and abroad to share the experience in implementing the pilot project as well as the results. As a result of the replication measures of the project, it is planned that at least one project will be</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	implemented in another waste management region in Latvia or abroad by the end of 2028. The replication measures are going to be implemented until the end of 2027.

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2014	Changes in company owners: the beginning of change and development.
2	2019	The State Environmental Service granted the company a waste management permit for a polluting activity – wood waste crushing.
3	Since 2020	Investments in technological equipment and employees.
4	2022	Owing to an increase in the prices of fossil energy, the price of wood chips and the demand for wood chips increased significantly. The company successfully continued to shift from supplying a chipping service to a full chipping cycle from the purchase of raw materials to the sale of the finished product – wood chips.
5	Since 2022	Involvement in the EU LIFE integrated project Waste To Resources Latvia – Boosting Regional Sustainability and Circularity by Introducing the Concept of Using Waste as Resources (LIFE Waste To Resources IP) (2021-2028). During the implementation of the project activity, it is planned to install a trial production line that demonstrates the possibility of producing sawdust blocks from wood waste and adding textile waste as an additional input during the block production process.
6	2023	The company found a supplier of equipment for engineering an innovative equipment prototype for processing wood and textile waste into chip blocks.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	The company uses local raw materials (wood waste) in its economic activity, and the product (chips) produced is sold in the national (Latvian) market. The company's economic activity contributes to sustainable thinking and the circular wood economy at the local level.
team and network	5	The main resources of the company are its public reputation, business relations with sustainably-minded cooperation partners in the market of Latvia, employees and experience obtained.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	By processing wood waste in a responsible way, various kinds of wood products are returned to the national economy in the form of both safe fuel for heating and inputs for the production of new products, thereby contributing to sustainable thinking and the circular wood economy.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	5	<p>To process wood waste safely and in accordance with the relevant legal framework, it is necessary to obtain a number of permits for waste collection, sorting and processing as well as for the sites intended for these activities. Only this guarantees the manufacture of a safe final product and further progress in the circular economy. Processing wood waste in a responsible way is a very visible example of the circular wood economy. Wood waste processing could be realistically scalable, and the idea could be replicated in other European rural areas.</p> <p>Currently, the company works on engineering pilot equipment and a technological process prototype, as well as the respective documentation, for processing wood and textile waste into blocks to be used in producing wooden shipping pallets and elsewhere.</p> <p>To share the experience in implementing the pilot project and the results, it is planned to hold online seminars for waste management companies in other regions</p>

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
		of Latvia and abroad. As a result of the replication measures of the project, it is planned that at least one project is implemented in another waste management region in Latvia or abroad by the end of 2028. The replication measures are going to be implemented until the end of 2027.
financial sustainability	5	A sustainable product that reduces the pressure on the environment, business relations with sustainably-minded cooperation partners, a long-term vision of the company's management regarding business expansion, investing profits in business development are prerequisites for financial sustainability.
social cohesion	5	Processing wood waste in a responsible way practically contributes to sustainable and green thinking and the circular wood economy.

Relevant links

1. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AXkWEOjWkMU>
2. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4A1Zvsx5RIg&t=1s>
3. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G2F8stoby7k>

4.2.1.2 Conclusion

Druplat contributes to closing the circle of wood processing activities, thus reducing the environmental impact of outdated wood waste management practices and preserving wood material's value, by giving a second life to wood waste. Most importantly, Druplat's activities showcase the main parameters that an efficient, sustainable and CO-oriented waste management system should take into account, meaning having good knowledge of the qualitative characteristics of the stream to be managed, so as to implement suitable ways of treatment and utilisation, and considering the stream as resource, i.e. continuously seeking for existing or new opportunities to reintroduce these wasted materials to the market (e.g. as raw materials for the development of innovative products).

4.3 Bioeconomy Theme: Aquatic and Water Systems
4.3.1 Algae Spirulina: tasty superfood for health and energy
4.3.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Algae Spirulina: tasty superfood for health and energy.
Subtitle - tagline	Algae spirulina is a unique product rich in antioxidants. In Latvia, a bioreactor has been created for these tropical algae, so that it can be grown at an even higher quality in the northern climate. It is harvested and frozen fresh or prepared in berry juice or syrup to preserve valuable substances and antioxidants as much as possible. These products surprise with a pleasant berry taste in contrast to the well-known specific taste of spirulina powder. It can be purchased in the SpirulinaNord e-store (delivery throughout the EU) and stores throughout Latvia.
Bioeconomy theme	Aquatic/Water Systems, Food & Agriculture
Core Activities	Algae spirulina cultivation in bioreactors, processing and sale; research, creation of new products (from spirulina), and consumer education.
Full Address	Piķurgas iela 36, Vālodzes, Stopiņu novads, LV-2130, Latvia. https://www.spirulinanord.eu/
No of employees	3 (in 2022)
Funding sources	The company finances its activities from its resources, grants, and investors' funds.

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	<p>Spirulina of the company "SpirulinaNord" is obtained at its production facility in Latvia, in unique bioreactors designed by the company itself. The innovative cultivation technology ensures the highest product quality, purity, and nutritional value. In addition, it has a neutral taste and smell, as opposed to the specific taste of most spirulina powder from other manufacturers. The company offers frozen spirulina, as well as products created according to its recipes - spirulina in berry syrup and juice - products that are rich in antioxidants, and amino acids, providing an influx of energy to the body.</p>
Detailed Description	<p>Spirulina is a unique microalgae that is one of the most nutrient-dense foods on the planet, naturally containing proA, E, and B vitamins, bioavailable iron, calcium, and zinc, as well as all essential amino acids.</p> <p>"SpirulinaNord" are the only growers of the tropical algae spirulina this far in the North. The founders of the company have created a technology suitable for the northern climate to grow spirulina in Latvia. Spirulina is grown 12 months a year in bioreactors - in a closed system, excluding insects and environmental pollution from entering the product, therefore it is maximally safe and the quality does not change under the influence of weather or environmental pollution, the use of pesticides and similar substances is not required, therefore the product is considered ecologically grown. "SpirulinaNord" technology is efficient in terms of consumption of natural resources (land, water, and minerals), which is ensured by high-level process optimisation and automation.</p> <p>Many do not believe it, but the founders of the company have built the spirulina cultivation system with their own hands, completely from scratch according to their design - no one has such a nursery. Fresh spirulina drinks are also an innovation on a global scale.</p> <p>The "SpirulinaNord" product range includes fresh spirulina in apple juice, quince, or cranberry syrup - such products are currently not produced anywhere else in the world. The products are not pasteurised to preserve all biologically active substances in them as much as possible.</p> <p>The company still offers fresh frozen spirulina, which was the first product and is very popular among independent customers, especially suitable for diabetics. Some other top spirulina growers elsewhere in the world also offer frozen spirulina. However, 99% of the spirulina powder is available on the market – often with a specific aroma and 80% loss of nutritional value due to drying.</p> <p>Spirulina is the best vegetable in the world! It is of high quality, does not upset the stomach, and is easily absorbed by the body even in case of indigestion. "SpirulinaNord" spirulina is a naturally grown product, without pesticides and other poisons. Spirulina does not contain allergens. The health effects of spirulina have been studied for decades. Clinically proven health benefits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lowers cholesterol level and blood pressure;

The Success Story Profile	
	<p> Reduces inflammatory processes, which are also the basis of many other diseases.</p> <p>The huge number of antioxidants in spirulina prevents health disorders caused by stress. It is a natural vitamin complex of vitamins C and E, provitamin A and B, it contains all the essential amino acids like meat, but it is not an animal product, and it also contains iron, which is absorbed 30% better than artificial iron preparations. Therefore, it is counted among superfoods, which is a group of natural food products with particularly high nutritional value. The unique composition of spirulina and the high absorption capacity of biologically active substances give immediate energy and improve well-being in the long term.</p> <p>Due to the high nutritional value of spirulina, the demand for it is growing rapidly in the world. In addition, its cultivation is environmentally friendly, so NATO and the UN recognise it as the food of the future.</p>
The team behind the story	<p>The founders of the company are two female scientists who are passionate biotechnologists with a desire to create new, sustainable products for human health.</p> <p>Dr.sc.ing. Agnese Stunda Zujeva, a long-time researcher at the Faculty of Materials Science and Applied Chemistry of the Riga Technical University (RTU) and doctor of engineering, believes that "The planet will be saved by those who know how to create more ecological and economical solutions". There are relatively few researchers in Latvia who have become entrepreneurs. This is the biggest difference between the scientists of this company. After 15 years of work, Agnese quite radically changed both the field - from ceramics to biotechnology - and science at the university to science-based business. The microalgae spirulina is the perfect product for me – the result is visible quickly and you don't have to wait several months until something has or hasn't grown, unlike strawberries or potatoes.</p> <p>The other co-founder of the company and the author of the idea – Dr.sc.ing. Kristīne Veģere was previously the leading researcher at the Water Research and Environmental Biotechnology Laboratory of the Riga Technical University. Kristine researches and develops renewable energy projects. A special role in her life is the study of sustainable lifestyle and nutrition, not only through the prism of consumption but also through the prism of production/cultivation.</p> <p>By developing the idea and attracting Kaspars Veģeris, experienced in the business environment, together formed a strong team, that founded the company SpirulinaNord. In five years, the idea has gone through all stages of commercialisation, from the laboratory scale to the industrial scale.</p>
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>The target audience is anyone who wants a natural product to increase health and energy. Latvia's demand is still not met, but the main emphasis is placed on the development of the company and products in export markets. Also, they offer other companies the opportunity to incorporate fresh spirulina into their food products.</p>
Vision and Future plans	<p>If a healthy diet is unpalatable or smells bad, it is difficult to consume it for a long time. This is the problem for anyone who has tried the widely available spirulina powder. Most of the spirulina powder is available on the market in compressed tablets - to make it easier to take.</p> <p>SpirulinaNord, on the other hand, pays special attention to ensuring that the created product is tasty and enjoyable to use. The founders emphasise that fresh, good-quality</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>spirulina is tasteless and odourless, and as long as it is not heat-treated, it is also of maximum value - just like berries. One of the most frequent compliments comes from mothers with picky children who are surprised that the children drink the dark green spirulina, they do it very willingly.</p> <p>The co-founder of the company says that until now the growth of the company was relatively slow because the team built and tested each subsequent bioreactor to perfect the technology. Now that the technology has been perfected and tested, faster development can begin.</p> <p>The company connects the development not only with a more powerful production plant and market in Latvia but also with exports to Germany and other countries where the German language is mostly used. In the future, the company is also considering technology licensing, offering customers abroad not only a finished product but also the opportunity to produce it themselves. Cultivation of spirulina in closed systems is possible in different parts of the world, even in markets that are not easy to conquer. No one else on the market currently offers climate-independent bioreactors specifically for spirulina. Spirulina can be used not only as a healthy food but also as a functional additive in the production of other food products.</p> <p>The company estimates the European market for fresh spirulina to be larger than the market for spirulina powder, which is EUR 542 million per year. True, fresh spirulina is currently considered a small-scale lifestyle business in Europe that cannot compete with China's dominance. SpirulinaNord, on the other hand, aims to offer fresh spirulina to Europeans on a completely different scale, dreaming that one-day spirulina will be consumed as often as coffee, as it is a much more valuable source of energy. In 2023, more than 220,000 servings of fresh spirulina were produced. The plan for 2024 -2025 is to increase the volume at least 10 times per year.</p>

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2017	The idea of growing spirulina sparked.
2	2018	The first laboratory-scale breeding attempts of spirulina have begun. The first version of the business plan was created thanks to participation in RTU IdeaLAB.
3	2019	The first 200L bioreactor prototype was created with the support of EIT ClimateKIC, registration in Food and Veterinary Service (PVD) and spirulina cultivation and frozen spirulina sales started.
4	2020	Victory in the SEB grant program for Inspiration, and participation in the Buildit business accelerator.
5	2021	The first 600L bioreactor prototype has been created and moving to larger premises is underway, an online store has been created, and spirulina-berry syrups have been created.
6	2022	The first prototype of the 1000L bioreactor was created, the brand design was developed and a more active activity in social media was started.
7	2023	At the beginning of 2023, the ninth bioreactor for the production of spirulina was installed in the company's pilot plant. 600 thousand euros have been attracted from the accelerator "Buildit Latvia", a private investor and the aquaculture grant program of the Rural Support Service. With this funding, a modern biotechnology production plant is being built in Riga, increasing the spirulina cultivation capacity more than 10 times.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	<p>Currently, the largest companies in the algae sector in Europe mostly catch macroalgae in the Atlantic Ocean, some grow it in the ocean. 99% of the tropical microalgae spirulina available on the market is powder from Asian farms.</p> <p>"SpirulinaNord" is a pioneer in the development of the microscopic algae spirulina technology, which is suitable for the Northern European climate and is compact - suitable for the areas where land costs a lot. The goal is European-grown spirulina for Europeans – shortening supply chains and promoting traceability.</p> <p>"Alternative aquaculture is developing rapidly in Europe, we have to occupy the spirulina niche!"</p>
team and network	5	<p>The team includes both scientists-engineers with business experience, which are unique interdisciplinary skills and knowledge that are rare, and the co-founders of the company have successfully attracted and are using various funds, grants, and investors.</p>
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	<p>"Spirulina is almost climate neutral. It is the best choice for those who care about the future of the planet", the representatives of the company say.</p> <p>In the future, the company is also considering licensing the production technology, to offer to customers abroad not only a finished product but also the opportunity to produce it themselves. Cultivation of spirulina in closed systems is possible in various parts of the world, including markets that are not easy to conquer. Currently, no one else offers climate-independent bioreactors specifically for spirulina.</p>
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	5	<p>The company has developed the cultivation of spirulina indoors by building bioreactors, testing and developing this technology, which is unique in the world. The company has introduced spirulina available in fresh form, which is of higher value because the important substances are not degraded during thermal processing, and it has a neutral taste and smell.</p> <p>The company innovatively produces spirulina, an automated and efficient facility that simulates tropical lakes, and the production is independent of climate and weather. The technology is compact and efficient, which allows algae to be grown both in the United Arab Emirates and beyond the Arctic Circle. The company estimates that this method requires fewer resources than traditional technology that relies on the sun. The reactors are designed according to the plug-and-play method - they are easy to multiply, move, and install. The company has an e-shop and cooperation with local and exporting companies.</p>
financial sustainability	4	<p>The company was founded in 2019 and is developing rapidly. The turnover triples every year, but the company intensively makes use of investments, and thus there are currently losses for the time being. In 2023, 600 thousand euros were attracted from the accelerator "Buildit Latvia", a private investor, and the aquaculture grant program of the Rural Support Service to increase the capacity of spirulina cultivation more than 10 times.</p>
social cohesion	5	<p>SpirulinaNord's mission is based on offering a product that improves public health - valuable spirulina. Grown locally - giving work to local people, not importing products from third countries. The organisation communicates honestly and openly with its employees and customers - demonstrating cultivation technology, informing them about the role of nutrition in health, and responsible attitude towards the environment and society. The company has entered the deposit program before it is</p>

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
		required by law. The company develops new products using products offered by Latvian farmers. Anyone who needs spirulina in larger quantities, regardless of family or disability status, receives discounts when shopping in the store.

Relevant links

1. Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fLpsrLxNE6I>
2. EuroNews: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Cvr7b6pOpNk>
3. 2019/2020 SEB grant video <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zlg26Y34Kzo>

4.3.1.2 Conclusion

“Algae Spirulina: tasty superfood for health and energy” is a successful endeavour in the alternative aquaculture sector, gathering a variety of desired features to act as a best practice example. With emphasis on research and testing, “Algae Spirulina” seeks to bring to the market products of high quality, purity, and nutritional value, which are produced in a sustainable way, while also contributing to the empowerment of local communities and the development of resilient food solutions.

4.4 Bioeconomy Theme: Biomaterials and Bioproducts

4.4.1 APIMI - Natural bee cosmetics manufacturer

4.4.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	APIMI - Natural bee cosmetics manufacturer
Subtitle - tagline	Natural cosmetics contain products created by bees: honey, wax, propolis, and others. Bee products come from Piebalga apiaries in Latvia, which are located in the forest, there are no cultivated areas near them, which ensures the quality of the products.
Bioeconomy theme	Biomaterials and bioproducts
Core Activities	Beekeeping/Apiculture, biocosmetics from bee-created products, apitherapy health improvement research.
Full Address	Pils, Ineši, Cēsis municipality, LV-4123, Latvia.
No of employees	2
Funding sources	Own financing, loan from owners, ALTUM loan, Investment and Development Agency of Latvia (LIAA) support programs.

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	Apimi is a family enterprise and idea in many generations, where the idea of founding the company was inspired by the father’s and grandfather’s love for bees and beekeeping, which now has been further developed by the sisters Madara and Ieva, taking over beekeeping, obtaining bee products, and developing them further: creating natural cosmetic products with bee products embedded in them: beeswax, propolis, and honey.
Detailed Description	Apimi is a company that operates in the countryside of Latvia - Vecpiebalga, outside the hustle and bustle of big cities, in peace and closer to nature, bees, and people. The path to the creation of Apimi has already started in the childhood of the sisters, both helping their father to pour honey, hold a smokehouse, and catch bee swarms, and listening to their father's stories about bees and their importance in people's lives. These stories and works have helped shape the essence of Apimi - to care for and respect people and nature all around. Traditional products - honey and propolis - are taken and developed further, creating health-essential and healing natural products, reducing product surpluses and making maximum use of products created by bees, obtaining new, high-added-value

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>products. In Latvian weather conditions, when it is windy and cold, the skin experiences dryness and roughness, which can be prevented and improved by biocosmetics obtained from natural bee products.</p> <p>Bees are the main pollinators of plants. It has been scientifically estimated that one-third of humanity's food supply depends on plant pollination, and most of this process is carried out by European honey bees. The more one learns about bees, the more they inspire the founders of the company. Did you know that beeswax is synthesised by the bee itself? Bee can regulate the amount of wax by herself, which means that if it is necessary to build new rooms where to put honey, the bee gives signals in her body to start synthesizing wax. The bee uses propolis not only as "warming" in the hive but also as a disinfectant. Before the honey is placed in the comb, the bee applies a thin layer of propolis and only then puts the honey inside. If a mouse is spotted sneaking into the hive for food, the bees sting it and wrap it in propolis, thus embalming it and ensuring that it does not contaminate the hive. These are just a few facts. Bee products are unique and rich in vitamins and minerals, they have various properties such as rejuvenating, antibacterial, anti-fungal, and others that Apimi products have. For now, the Apimi company is engaged in the production of natural cosmetics that incorporate bee products, but in the future, they want to develop products that could be used for apitherapy.</p> <p><i>Apitherapy is a complementary treatment method that complements conventional medicine with methods and products used in apitherapy, using all beekeeping products - honey, wax, propolis, bee bread, pollen, royal jelly, and bee venom.</i></p>
The team behind the story	<p>It is a Latvian company created by two sisters Madara and Ieva. The sisters are inspired by their father, who is a beekeeper, who inherited it from his father, also a beekeeper. This company was created by a multi-generational family, where the two sisters, experimenting, have created new products for beauty, everyday life, and health alongside traditional honey. In this family, the parents have instilled in the sisters a love for bees, nature, and work since childhood.</p> <p>The owners of the company have a desire to share their values and let everyone feel the effect of bee products on beauty and well-being.</p> <p>The natural cosmetics produced by Apimi contain products created by bees: honey, wax, propolis, and others. The bee products come from Piebalga apiaries, which are located in the woods, there are no cultivated areas near them, which ensures the quality of the obtained products. The products manufactured by Apimi contain natural and certified raw materials, and regular work is underway to create new products.</p> <p>Apimi products are produced with respect for nature and care for the customer and the environment! Cosmetics are not tested on animals; product testing takes place in an independent and accredited laboratory.</p> <p>The slogan of the company is: Inspired by Bees - Created by Apimi!</p> <p><i>Madara</i>, the co-creator of Apimi, has obtained a Bachelor of Engineering in Chemical Technology from the Riga Technical University (RTU), and a Master of Engineering in Food Science from the Latvia University of Agriculture. Madara has work experience in the pharmaceutical and cosmetics industry. She is responsible for production in the company, from the idea to the creation of new products in their final version, including the customisation and automation of equipment. Apimi's factory is her kingdom. Apimi alternates work duties with raising a son. Her main duties: 1) processes the bee products</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>collected from their apiaries, so that they can be incorporated into cosmetic products; 2) works on the creation of new products; 3) produces existing products by constantly automating production processes; 4) improvement of documentation and product testing.</p> <p>Future goals – to process bee products even more differently and in different ways, to create new cosmetic products that would differ from those available on the market, and to improve our everyday lives. She would like to specialise more in collecting and processing bee products to improve efficiency.</p> <p><i>Ieva</i>, the co-creator of Apimi, has a bachelor's degree from RTU and a master's degree in Engineering - Construction. In addition (in the form of courses) has acquired accounting, record-keeping, and export skills. Ieva is in charge of the numbers and everything related to sales. Some will say it's boring (bookkeeping, record keeping, reports, and projects), but she likes it. Probably, the already-acquired education and love for numbers and calculations allow you to work with real passion. She creates and monitors the company website, and Ieva is the person who receives and responds to messages that can be sent in the "chat" box of the website or in any other way. Processes and fulfills both individual people and store orders. Participates in fairs and exhibitions, representing Apimi. She maintains communication and looks for new cooperation partners. Her everyday life is very full and colourful, she can't complain about boredom and routine. There are times when you have to become a programmer and break into the world of "code", and there are times when you have to be a mom despite the responsibilities and to-do list. Her daily life could be described as balancing between family and business.</p> <p>Future goals – she wants to create a new website, it requires new knowledge, time, and creativity. Would like to see Apimi products on the shelves of larger stores and to send regular shipments of products outside the borders of Latvia.</p>
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>Production – natural cosmetics and health improvement products, which are sold mainly in Latvia, but a small part is also exported to Hungary, Switzerland, Great Britain, Austria, and other countries, using the online store and export shipments. Customers are mainly private individuals and legal entities, the company also offers corporate gifts for both women and men.</p>
Vision and Future plans	<p>To develop products for apitherapy, to process bee products even more differently and in different ways, to create new means that would improve our everyday life and differ from those available on the market. They want to specialise more in collecting and processing bee products to improve efficiency. Thinking about how to increase recognition, and awareness of the unique properties of bee products and products produced by the company, how to improve customers' shopping experience, and develop a new company website. We want to develop and expand the sale of Apimi products in larger stores, so that everyone can see and choose, as well as increasingly send out regular shipments of products outside the borders of Latvia.</p>

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2018-2019	<p>Perhaps the idea came a little earlier, but it was formulated and took real shape during this time. Obtained financing with a business plan - we wrote a business plan and obtained the first 5000 euros (grant) to start our business. The first equipment, raw materials, packaging, and rent of small premises from the county, but the main was establishing a company.</p>

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
2	10-2019	We entered the business incubator almost immediately after establishing the SIA (limited liability company). Mentors, various trainings, and of course, funding were great supports at the very beginning of the business.
3	4-2020	Creating Apimi's online store. Along with the start of the company, Covid was also born in the world and the creation of an online store was especially important. It gave experience in things we did for the first time - creating an online store. But no matter how difficult the beginning seemed, at the moment owners are happy that they can manage their trades by themselves, without a programmer's support.
4	Spring-2021	VOUCHER – propolis extract research. Science and in-depth knowledge of what the company does is our guiding principle not only in business. Owners both have master's degrees and believe in knowledge-based facts. That's why, when they were creating the first business plan, they thought about the fact that they would like to invest their funds in research. They did not expect that it would happen so quickly, but it was a great pleasure and satisfaction that already in the 2nd year of operation they were able to conduct research and find out the activity of the propolis collected in their beehives. And the results were even more pleasing - the activity indicators of Latvian, Piebalga propolis are ten times better than in Central Europe.
5	1-2023	Within the framework of the LEADER program – exhibition and purchase of production equipment with ALTUM co-financing. To start a more serious export, it was important to increase the production capacity without losing quality. Therefore, a decision was made to enter the LEADER competition to obtain a grant of 65% and to be able to build a production facility. This was a big job that took less than two years in total, a lot of time, and nerves, but it turned out great. In January 2023, the long-awaited equipment was installed, which allowed to increase the production volume and reduce the cost.
6	Summer, autumn-2023	Testing of production equipment, and adaptation to work. The whole year was spent in testing, checking the products, adjusting the equipment, and practicing. But, at the moment, company is happy that everything is working as expected.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	The resource is local, the company is located in the countryside of Latvia - Vecpiebalga, and the company has its beehives, from which the bees pollinate the nearby meadows and fields, as a result of which both honey and other products are formed in the hive. Then natural cosmetics and health products are created. The process ensures that the product is obtained from the meadows of Vecpiebalga and is sustainably managed and produced. Even the packaging is made of environmentally friendly materials.
team and network	5	Both co-owners are sisters who form a very strong team, one sister complementing the other by sharing work and specialisation. The sisters have inherited a love for bees and beekeeping from their father and grandfather, the beekeeping they have learned in childhood, has been developed into sustainable and innovative products. Each owner has both academic education and practical experience and export through the online store to other EU and EEA countries is ensured. The local

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
		ecosystem is created by the company and is being developed as both owners study in the LIAA business incubator.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	4	<p>Natural cosmetics is a niche product, because there is a lot of competition for the consumer in the cosmetic markets, both from the products of natural cosmetics producers and conventional producers, but bee products have several healing properties, which make bee products very attractive to replace conventionally produced cosmetics.</p> <p>Beekeeping has a positive impact on the environment, pollination of fields is especially important so that the harvest can ripen. Honey is by far the best-known bee product in linear agriculture, but the company, through research and experiments, has created natural cosmetics and health-promoting products for daily use, without the use of chemicals, only from natural products, increasing the added value in beekeeping and ensuring efficient use of resources.</p>
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	5	<p>The company itself conducts research and experiments, the owners have participated in the business incubator organised by LIAA, and co-financing has been obtained in the VAUČER program to develop a study on the methodology for the extraction of propolis glycerin and propolis alcohol extracts, determining the content of active substances in propolis extracts.</p> <p>Various applications of bee products are tested daily in the company's production facility and new products are created, which are sold in the company's online store and exported to foreign countries in small quantities. It is possible to create similar companies in Europe, where bees are raised and kept, but there is a need for nearby fields where conventional farming does not take place so that honey and other obtained products are organic because then it is possible to create and develop both cosmetic products and health-enhancing products in the corresponding European region.</p>
financial sustainability	4	<p>The company is new, as it was founded in 2019. In 2021, it employed one person, in 2022 - already 2. In 2022, the company worked with a turnover of EUR 29 thousand and a profit of EUR 876. Since the company is new, it is developing because the fixed assets for the production of cosmetics have been purchased and in cooperation with LIAA, research and experiments are carried out for the creation of new products. Therefore, the expansion of the range of new products, an increase in sales, and an increase in profits are expected in the future. An opportunity to increase the number of employees in the company is planned, which is especially important in rural areas. The company has current assets exceeding current liabilities by 1.6 times and has positive equity, equity, and return on assets ratios. The company invests undistributed profit in the development of the company; therefore, no dividends were paid in 2021 and 2022.</p>
social cohesion	5	<p>By developing beekeeping in the countryside, the company promotes pollination of the surrounding meadows and fields, thus ensuring the ripening and development of the crop in the countryside. The location of the company in the countryside contributes to the production of high-quality products, as there are no conventionally cultivated fields around, thus it is possible to obtain natural organic products. Working and establishing a production plant in a rural area promotes employment and the development of the region. No negative impacts on the community are observed.</p>

Relevant links

1. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fu_VsL08S5Q

4.4.1.2 Conclusion

APIMI serves as a success story in the field of bioproducts, i.e. natural cosmetics, through the adoption of environmentally friendly production methods, such as the location of apiaries, the product testing methods and the maximum utilisation of beekeeping products, that not only result in the development of eco-friendly products, via sustainable use of resources, but also affects the neighboring areas and ecosystems in a positive way, both environmentally (pollination of fields) and socially (job creation).

4.4.2 Power of Plants

4.4.2.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Power of Plants
Subtitle - tagline	We know how to capture the power of plants in products!
Bioeconomy theme	Biomaterials and bioproducts
Core Activities	Production of an environment-, pet- and human-friendly plant protection product (garlic hydrolate) and products (plant (fir, mint, blackcurrant leaf, garlic) hydrolates) valuable for humans from locally sourced raw materials by applying the steam distillation technique.
Full Address	153 Birzite, Viesturciems vilage, Gluda parish, Latvia
No of employees	2. Augu spēks Ltd (Power of Plants) a family business employing a team of four people: both parents and their two children.
Funding sources	Own-financing, funding from the EU Structural Funds (LEADER), funding won at national business idea competitions.

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	Augu spēks Ltd produces plant-based edible and non-edible products by applying the steam distillation techniques. The family business contributes to the bioeconomy because its products are 100% natural, without artificial additives, retain unique properties of plants and are an excellent alternative to products manufactured industrially from raw materials of petroleum origin. To produce garlic hydrolate, the family business also buys discarded garlic from local farmers, which would otherwise represent agricultural waste.
Detailed Description	The business idea – to process garlic in an innovative way, applying the bioeconomy approach – was based on the entrepreneurs' own observations: the owners noticed that after garlic had been harvested, some of it was sold, while quite a lot of it was the so-called “junk” – mechanically damaged, non-standard garlic –, which was not really a marketable commodity anymore and also not planting material. Such spoiled garlic was most often considered agricultural waste and discarded, but it still contained the valuable properties of garlic. The entrepreneurs believed that this was not right because the resources were wasted, the product was produced but not sold and put to good use. Therefore, they looked for ideas of what could be done with the spoiled garlic. The entrepreneurs studied various research papers and the experience of other countries and concluded that garlic is a very effective repellent of plant pests. For hundreds, maybe even thousands of years, garlic has been used in China and India where natural protection agents are still very popular, whereas in Europe when the industrialisation era began, many ancient pieces of popular wisdom have been forgotten, and natural plant protection agents are used much less.

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>Besides, the nature and conviction of the entrepreneurs themselves did not allow the use of artificial plant protection products in their garden; therefore, they had been experimenting with natural plant protection products for years to find out which was the most effective one to control garden pests.</p> <p>The entrepreneurs also emphasise that the public’s mindset and perception of life are also changing, and there is an increasing demand for nature- and health-friendly products in all areas of life, incl. in the field of plant protection.</p> <p>Based on their personal experience and observations, the scientific research findings and their interdisciplinary knowledge, the entrepreneurs created a product – garlic hydrolate (called Garlic Power) –, which provides natural protection against garden pests. The product consists of 100% garlic hydrolate or a mixture of distilled water and essential oils. The active principles contained in garlic (e.g. diallyl disulfide, organic sulphur compounds, isomenthone etc.) are effective against a wide range of garden pests. The product can be used as an alternative to synthetic pesticides. It is easy to use and store, non-toxic, safe for children and pets, does not affect the taste of fruits, berries or vegetables, harmless to invertebrates that benefit plants. It adds value to potential agricultural waste as a product produced from discarded garlic. This product and the approach to the production thereof is an innovation for the Latvian market, as Augu spēks Ltd is the only enterprise that produces this kind of product. Garlic hydrolats produced in other countries (e.g. USA, India, China) are available in foreign online shops.</p> <p>Over time, the entrepreneurs realised that garlic hydrolat is a seasonal product, and it is necessary to expand the range of products by starting to produce also hydrolats from other plants (fir, mint, blackcurrant leaves, garlic), which can be used for skin and hair care, room air freshening and disinfection, sauna rituals, as well as spices from garlic and onions and healthy nibbles can be made from quinces, raspberries and rhubarb.</p>
The team behind the story	<p>The education received by the owners of the family business has helped to develop this business idea and start their own business. The wife has a master's degree in biology (Mg. Biol.) and a doctoral degree in economics (Dr. oec.), which provided interdisciplinary and deep knowledge for developing the business idea and starting the business. The husband, however, has an engineering education and good technical knowledge of the product production process, his education and work experience while working as a surveyor has also contributed to his good management and organisational skills, accuracy, a high sense of responsibility, which are important cornerstones for a successful business. Therefore, the husband is responsible for the product production process, procurement of resources and raw materials, quality control, sale of finished products, while the wife is the idea generator and developer responsible for the accumulation and transfer of knowledge, communication with cooperation partners and customers, marketing activities and family business image formation.</p> <p>Important helpers are their children who are actively involved at all stages of activities of the family business, from growing agricultural inputs, packing and packaging products to selling the products at farmers’ fairs. The children are also responsible for photography and making and editing videos.</p>
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>Farmers, horticultural farms.</p> <p>Cooperation partners: the association Rural Partnership “Lielupe” and local garlic producers.</p>

The Success Story Profile	
Vision and Future plans	<p>Currently, it is a family business that wants to gradually increase its capacity, so that its development takes place organically, step by step. The entrepreneurs want their family business to be known in Jelgava municipality, Latvia and beyond. The owners perceive their business not as a business but an ideological project. Both parents have main jobs and the family business is an additional occupation started in the name of an idea. It involves more of an educational, informative and supportive function. The vision of the family business is to instruct and advise others, so that it results in a wider resonance. Earning money is a secondary objective. The entrepreneurs want people to find out, get educated and be interested in natural alternative products that exist and are created from plants grown in Latvia. The mission of the family business is to foster the development of waste-free production and add value to agricultural products that are not suitable for sale, thus making a practical contribution to the bioeconomy and green thinking. Therefore, the main goal of the family business is to offer farmers sustainable and efficient solutions, supporting their transition to a greener future.</p>

Milestones Timeline		
	Date	Milestone
1	8-2019	The creation of a business idea. Participation in the business idea competition “Being an Entrepreneur in Jelgava Municipality 2019” held by the government of Jelgava municipality. The municipality has provided financial support in the amount of EUR 700.
2	10-2019	Foundation of Augu spēks Ltd
3	4-2020	Starting production by applying the steam distillation technique.
4	10-2020	LEADER funding for purchasing equipment.
5	10-2020	Expanding the range of products and starting the production of new products.
6	2021	Expanding the range with new products. Active participation of the family business in farmers’ fairs and advertising the family business in social media (promotion of the brand of the family business).

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	To produce the products, the family business uses only locally sourced agricultural inputs, which are grown on their own farm, as well as purchased from local producers. By producing garlic hydrolate, the family business also helps local farmers to dispose of damaged garlic, which would otherwise be discarded. The products are as natural as possible, contain no artificial additives and retain the unique properties of plants in a concentrated form; therefore, the family business offers farmers a sustainable and effective solution, supporting their transition to a greener future.
team and network	3	Currently, it is a family business, and both parents’ interdisciplinary knowledge and skills, as well as professional experience have been important cornerstones for successfully starting up and developing the business, while in the future, the business’s capacity is going to be gradually increased, so that the development takes place organically, step by step. Funding from the national business idea competition and LEADER project proposal competitions was used for business development, and significant support was received from the association Rural Partnership “Lielupe”.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
		The family business cooperates with other Jelgava municipality companies, holds joint informational events and farmers' fairs, thereby maintaining cooperation within the local business community.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	The products produced by the family business are as natural as possible, do not contain artificial additives and retain the unique properties of plants in a concentrated form; therefore, the family business offers farmers a sustainable and effective solution, supporting their transition to a greener future. By producing garlic hydrolat, Augu spēks Ltd helps local farmers to sell discarded garlic, thus making a practical contribution to the circular bioeconomy. The owners perceive their family business mostly as an ideological project: it performs more of an educational, informative and supportive function.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	5	The owners have been experimenting with natural plant protection products for years to find out which was the most effective one to control garden pests. Based on their personal experience and the scientific research findings, the entrepreneurs created a product – garlic hydrolate –, which provides natural protection against garden pests. Augu spēks Ltd is the only enterprise that produces this kind of product in Latvia. Garlic hydrolates produced in other countries (e.g. the USA, India, China) can be purchased in foreign online shops. The product is realistically scalable, the idea can be replicated in other European rural areas.
financial sustainability	4	Sustainable products aimed at reducing the burden on the environment, the patience, perseverance and long-term vision of the owners regarding business expansion and product range diversification as well as the investment of profits in business development are prerequisites for the financial sustainability of the family business.
social cohesion	5	The products produced by the family business are as natural as possible and contain the unique properties of plants in a concentrated form. The products make a practical contribution to the circular bioeconomy and green thinking. The products add value to potential agricultural waste. The entrepreneurs also want the public to find out, get educated and be interested in natural alternative products that exist and are created from plants grown in Latvia.

Relevant links

1. <http://www.auguspeks.lv/produkti/dabigi-augu-aizsardzibas-lidzekli/>
2. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VF6sHaQObCE>

4.4.2.2 Conclusion

“Power of Plants” is an excellent paradigm of a local circular bio-based solution, with community-oriented characteristics, which is also replicable. The team, putting in practice their interdisciplinary knowledge, focused on closing the loop of local materials and products, via properly treating plants (including garlic that would end up as agricultural waste) and developing natural products, which can also be used in local community’s activities (such as natural pesticides that could also be used by local farmers).

4.4.3 INSIGNES LABS

4.4.3.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	INSIGNES LABS
Subtitle - tagline	producer of innovative agricultural products
Bioeconomy theme	Biomaterials and Bioproducts
Core Activities	Development and production of environmentally-friendly plant protection products
Full Address	Kazimierza Wielkiego 43/2A, 30-074 Kraków
No of employees	7-20 depends on the need
Funding sources	Private, public

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	<p>Insignes Labs is developing safe, affordable, and environmentally-friendly fertilisers, biostimulants and plant protection products for farmers. Using our cutting-edge mineral-based PURE technology, we aim to boost crop growth, shield against stress, and lead to high-quality yield. Our expertise in plant physiology and biochemistry has driven the development of PURE technology, focusing on meeting the crop's needs for growth and development.</p>
Detailed Description	<p>The most effective defense against abiotic and biotic stress pathogens, especially fungal and bacterial diseases, is the inherent immunity of the plant itself. When this natural resistance is lacking, the introduction of an external factor, such as a plant protection product, becomes necessary. Natural plant immunity can be triggered by various organic substances and chemical elements. PURE TECHNOLOGY is a unique blend of inorganic molecules. It acts as a catalyst. It activates hundreds of enzymes and pathways. PURE ONE is based on 3 pillars. We call it SOS for crops:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Substitution: means slashing synthetic pesticide usage by up to 50% and synthetic fertilisers up to 20% 2) Optimisation: stays for activation of natural immunity against stresses and pathogens leading to healthier, more resilient crops. 3) Supplementation: Improved nutrient management, enhanced photosynthetic activity ultimately results in the boost of biomass production, contributing to the sequestration of CO₂. <p>Reducing carbon footprint is key. By slashing fungicide usage, we're making tangible reductions in CO₂ emissions per hectare.</p> <p>Building on this understanding, the first product based on PURE technology was created: PURE ONE®. This product employs three mechanisms to enhance plant health and productivity, whether facing biotic and abiotic stresses or in their absence.</p> <p>The comprehensive impact of PURE ONE® stems from the activation of natural plant metabolic pathways, leading to an overall improvement in plant condition and creating a protective shield against adverse growth conditions (abiotic stresses) and/or pathogens.</p> <p>PURE ONE has undergone testing and registration across a diverse range of crops: wheat, rapeseed, corn, soyabean, sugar beet, potatoes, grapes, berries, apples, and various vegetables. Field and registration trials have been conducted in Poland, Germany, Austria, the USA, and Saudi Arabia. PURE ONE® can be used as a tank mix with the majority of commonly used agrochemicals including synthetic and biological products. The benefits of</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>our PURE technology extend to both farmers and consumers. For farmers, it means improved productivity without harming the environment Consumers, on the other hand, enjoy high-quality, residue-free food on their plates.</p> <p>Insignes Labs developed portfolio of PURE products (PURE ONE, PURE VIGOR, PURE FRUIT AND PURE SEED) tailored to address specific agricultural needs, backed by rigorous validation processes across Europe and the USA through lab tests, greenhouse experiments, and over 200 field trials across 20+ crops globally.</p>
The team behind the story	<p>PhD Anna Ogar is a co-founder and CEO of Insignes Labs and Microbe Plus - a biotech startups. She received her PhD from international doctoral studies at Jagiellonian University, Freie Universität Berlin and the University of Örebro in Sweden. Dr. Ogar is the author of numerous publications on environmental and industrial microbiology. She received numerous awards and scholarships such as Alexander von Humboldt Stiftung/Foundation as well as a scholarship from the Foundation for Polish Science.</p>
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>Farmers</p> <p>WIALAN, Südzucker, Maspex, Farm Frites, Krajowa Grupa Spożywcza, BayWa // REM Analytics, The Institute of Plant Protection – National Research Institute (IPP – NRI), KAUST</p>
Vision and Future plans	<p>Embracing open innovation, our business model seeks partnerships to scale and launch our technology globally. Our ambition doesn't stop at one region. Our roadmap includes expanding product lines, seeking regulatory approvals in key markets (EU, USA, LATAM), and targeting Asian-Pacific countries.</p> <p>Our ultimate goal is to offer farmers sustainable and effective solutions, supporting their transition to a greener future.</p>

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	10-2018	Investment round
2	6-2019	Collaboration together with Battelle LTD company
3	3-2020	Receiving a R&D grant – Fast Track Found
4	4-2020	Hiring new employee Jerzy Prochnicki
5	10-2022	Regulatory approval of first product PURE ONE
6	1-2023	First distribution agreement on PURE technology

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	3	<p>Global Perspective: The focus on global, rather than just local, validation and launch indicates a commitment to catering to a diverse range of agricultural environments and practices worldwide.</p> <p>Local Engagement: Involving local farmers and food producers in the validation process helps in understanding the unique challenges and requirements of different regions, leading to better product adaptation.</p>
team and network	5	<p>Diverse Expertise: A multidisciplinary team with varied backgrounds and experiences is crucial for addressing the complex challenges associated with crop protection. It brings together different perspectives and skills necessary for successful R&D projects.</p>

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
		Accelerated Progress: Hiring individuals with a background in crop protection expedites the research and development process, ensuring a faster turnaround from concept to market-ready product.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	<p>Scepticism to Acceptance: Overcoming initial skepticism from companies and farmers regarding reduced synthetic chemical input signifies the success of the company's focus on low environmental impact products.</p> <p>Regulatory Trends: Alignment with regulatory bodies' push towards sustainability positions the company well in an industry increasingly emphasizing eco-friendly and greener practices.</p>
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	5	<p>International Trials: Securing budgets and forming partnerships to conduct trials across different geographies and crops is essential for comprehensive validation. International validation facilitates the scalability of the technology on a global level.</p> <p>Technology Scalability: Adequate resources enable the company to validate the technology effectively, ensuring its applicability across various agricultural settings.</p>
financial sustainability	5	<p>Challenges for Startups: Financial sustainability is a significant challenge for young companies, especially in highly regulated industries. The need for persistence and patience highlights the difficulty in securing funding for projects perceived as high risk.</p> <p>Long-Term Vision: The importance of maintaining a long-term vision despite initial financial challenges is a starting point in development of new technologies.</p>
social cohesion	4	Social Awareness: The shift in the food industry towards prioritizing healthy food and customer expectations signifies a broader societal awareness. This shift compels food chains to focus on quality rather than just pricing, creating opportunities for innovative and sustainable solutions.

The success of the business relies on a holistic approach that considers global perspectives, local engagement, diverse expertise, environmental consciousness, strategic partnerships, financial sustainability, and responsiveness to evolving societal expectations in the agriculture and food industry.

4.4.3.2 Conclusion

INSIGNES LABS, through the development of PURE technology, contributes to the transition to greener agricultural practices, where the minimisation of synthetic pesticides and fertilisers and the use of environmentally-friendly fertilisers, biostimulants and plant protection products lead to resilient crops, high productivity, reduction of CO2 emissions, and high-quality, residue-free food. The research and constant product validation in order to provide tailored solutions, according to the needs of different crops and environments is of great importance for the effectiveness of the provided solution.

4.5 Bioeconomy Theme: Bioenergy

4.5.1 Egg Energy Ltd

4.5.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Egg Energy Ltd
Subtitle - tagline	Poultry manure processing plant
Bioeconomy theme	Bioenergy
Core Activities	Biogas production from 100% chicken manure and production of innovative fertilisers from digestate.
Full Address	Head office, Iecava parish, LV-3913, Latvia
No of employees	16
Funding sources	Own-financing, EU funding, loans from natural persons and commercial banks

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	Biogas is produced exclusively from chicken manure, making Egg Energy Ltd one of the most unique cogeneration facilities. Biogas is used to produce electricity and thermal energy. The residual material from the biogas production process (fermented substrate) is transformed into a valuable organic fertiliser.
Detailed Description	<p>The company produces biogas from chicken manure. The technology is based on the anaerobic digestion process in which the raw material is broken down by bacteria under low oxygen conditions. Biogas is produced as a by-product. Biogas is used to produce electricity and thermal energy. The electrical capacity of the cogeneration facility is 2 MW and the amount of thermal energy generated is 2.1 MW. The company sells electricity to traders on the electricity exchange and uses part of it for self-consumption: the technological processes of biogas production and the production of organic fertilisers. The thermal energy is used for self-consumption.</p> <p>The residual material from the biogas production process (fermented substrate) is transformed into valuable, high-quality organic fertiliser OrganiQ (OrganiQ is a registered trademark of Egg Energy Ltd). Liquid ammonium sulphate concentrate (6000 m³/year) and granular fertiliser from the solid fraction of the fermented material (10000 t/year) are produced by processing the digestate by the three-stage osmosis technique. The high-quality granular organic fertiliser has a high content of organic matter, phosphorus (P), sulphur (S), magnesium (Mg) and calcium (Ca). The fertiliser contains the most important trace elements for crops: B, Mn, Mo, Cu and Zn. The application of organic fertilisers improves soil fertility.</p>
The team behind the story	The key to the success of Egg Energy Ltd is its employees and board members with their strategic vision and long-term work experience, as well as practical connections with a sustainably minded, ambitious cooperation partner – the JSC Balticovo (the largest producer of eggs and egg products in Northern Europe).
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>The digestate produced is sold to contractual partners (farmers) for fertilizing agricultural land, while dry digestate granules and concentrate are sold through retail chains (Kurši, Mājai und dārzam, Kurzeme sēklas, Depo) as well as regional small shops in Latvia. The company sells the green electricity generated to traders on the electricity exchange.</p> <p>The company cooperates with the JSC Balticovo (supply of bird manure and water), "Dzīvokļu komunālā saimniecība" Ltd (household waste management), FIXT Ltd</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>(maintenance and refuelling of refrigeration equipment), FILTER Latvia Ltd (operation and maintenance of cogeneration equipment, as well as waste management).</p> <p>The design and engineering office SEP (JSC "Siltumelektroprojekts") is also an important cooperation partner, which has developed a unique biogas production technology in the world that uses only chicken manure as an input. In the field of development support, Egg Energy Ltd cooperates with the Investment and Development Agency of Latvia.</p>
Vision and Future plans	<p>In 2022, Egg Energy Ltd invested in research and development to transform the current products into other innovative products with higher value added. The company developed a technological solution to the production of biomethane and green ammonia water solution. The products will be competitive in the domestic market and allow us to reduce the imports of fossil fuels and fertilisers and consequently the negative environmental impact, including the amount of greenhouse gas produced by both industries.</p> <p>In 2023, the company launched a modernisation project at the biogas facility, which would allow the company to increase the production capacity by even 50%, reaching 3 MW. This modernisation makes the Egg Energy biogas facility an even more efficient and sustainable source of “green” energy. By expanding the generation capacity, the facility can supply more energy to the local power grid, reducing dependence on fossil energy resources and contributing to green energy as well as sustainable development.</p>

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	04/2014-11/2015	The company implemented the project Innovative Production of Fertiliser from Digestate, the goal of which was to establish a facility to produce high-quality organic fertiliser – ammonium sulphate concentrate – through innovative digestate processing, which would be the only digestate processing facility installed in the Baltics. The project was co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund.
2	12/2015	The biogas cogeneration facility and the fertiliser production facility began operating.
3	2018-2019	The wordmark OrganiQ was registered with the Patent Board of the Republic of Latvia (20/08/2018) and the trademark OrganiQ was registered in the European Union (27/05/2019) (27/05/2019).
4	11/2018	An agreement was concluded with the Investment and Development Agency of Latvia for receiving support under the measure Promotion of International Competitiveness, which was co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund
5	2022	Research work was underway to transform the current products into innovative products.
6	2023	In cooperation with SEP, a modernisation project at the biogas facility was developed, which would allow the company to increase the biogas production capacity.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	The company uses only locally sourced raw materials to recycle and reuse them, as well as the expertise of local entrepreneurs.
team and network	5	Teamwork at the company level and cooperation with local companies: the JSC Balticovo, the production technology developer SEP, as well as the Investment and Development Agency of Latvia was the basis for the success of Egg Energy Ltd.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	By producing environment-friendly energy, the energy independence of the country is increased, the circular economy is fostered and harmful emissions are prevented from entering the atmosphere; however, supply chains are shortened and investments are made in the national economy of Latvia by using the competence and raw materials of local entrepreneurs. Transforming the by-products of biogas production into fertiliser supports the transition of farmers to a greener future, contributes to the circular economy and soil health and reduces dependence on imported fertilisers.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	4	SEP (Egg Energy's cooperation partner, which has designed and built the biogas facility) has developed a world-unique biogas production technology that uses only chicken manure as a raw material, as well as constructed a facility using this technology and maintains the operation thereof. SEP's unique biogas production technology has already proven itself and is in demand among customers. Currently, SEP implements several projects in other countries: the USA (3 projects) and Lithuania. Currently, SEP is also implementing the modernisation project at the Egg Energy biogas facility. SEP has patented the fertiliser production technology and registered it as ORGANIQ™. The research conducted by the LBTU Institute of Agriculture confirmed in 2017 that the fertiliser OrganiQ significantly increased the yield of wheat as a base fertiliser.
financial sustainability	5	Egg Energy Ltd creates new development solutions that ensure financial sustainability through investing funds in development and research as well as modernisation.
social cohesion	5	The economic activities of Egg Energy Ltd combine care for climate protection and soil health (by providing alternative sources of thermal energy and electricity as well as producing fertilisers and preventing harmful emissions from entering the atmosphere) and reduce dependence on the imports of fossil fuels and fertilisers.

Relevant links

1. <https://www.sep.lv/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/SEP-EGG-ENERGY-read-more.pdf>
2. <https://www.sep.lv/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/SEP-ORGANIQ-read-more.pdf>
3. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CwAV90oAYuw>
4. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nc2zUXawCgY>

4.5.1.2 Conclusion

Egg Energy Ltd showcases an integrated waste management system, where a waste stream is treated to create value through new products, primarily energy, coming from resources that would otherwise end up in landfills. In this way, residual biomass is valorised as a sustainable resource of renewable energy, contributing to the transition to cleaner forms of energy. At the same time, maximum utilisation of the process by-products is achieved, since the fermented substrate is transformed into valuable, high-quality organic fertiliser. Thus, this bio-based solution fully adopts circular practices and promotes the minimisation of unsustainable use of primary resources.

5 Identified Success Stories: South-West RBP

The section presents the identified success stories of the South-West RBP, including Spain, Portugal and Italy and represented in the project by AVEBIOM, UC, CBE and AIEL. The South-West RBP have already reached the KPI, since they have identified one success story per bioeconomy theme.

5.1 Bioeconomy Theme: Food & Agriculture

5.1.1 Re-using washing wastewater for irrigation

5.1.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Re-using olive washing wastewater for irrigation
Subtitle - tagline	Utilising olive washing wastewater for irrigation and improved fert-irrigation of olive fields
Bioeconomy theme	Food & Agriculture
Core Activities	Agrifood industry water recycling, Irrigation, Nutrient recycling
Full Address	Calle Decaradas, s/n, 23420 Canena, Jaén 38.04407960850527 N , 3.484560937939069 W
No of employees	Cooperative (300 farmers). 10 Technicians contracted.
Funding sources	Initial trials (since 2001) and set-up (from 2010): cooperative own funds Innovation action for extending the system and create evidence based data: Operational Group EIP-AGRI (EFARD funding)

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	The success case reflects how a farmers cooperative performed steps forward to valorise the wastewater from the olive washing and hoppers leakage. This involved a process of testing, the adoption of innovative solutions and the creation of confidence with a community of local irrigators. The adoption was successful and led in a second stage to a new innovation process to further apply the water to subsurface precision systems, and to also quantify the positive effects of the fertigation of this wastewater, like the cost savings and the positive effects on crop yields.
Detailed Description	<p>This case reflects the success in the reuse of an agroindustrial by-product, the olive washing wastewater. In Spain, as well as in the European Mediterranean area, most oil mills have to deal with this problem. In some cases this liquid wastewater is mixed with the olive cake or with the rest of the vegetable waters obtained in the process of olive oil extraction. A usual practice is to dispose in shallow ponds to facilitate evaporation, or even to force the evaporation by diffusing the water with sprinklers in the air, which entails additional energy consumption.</p> <p>The application of olive washing water is a practice with synergistic potential, since it can contribute to the crops in the area by increasing the amount of water available for irrigation, reducing the need to use fertilisers, and solving the management of this water residual, which implies costs and a loss of opportunity. This practice is regulated in Spain, although in order for these waters to be injected into a network of irrigation canals or pipes, it is necessary to have the approval of the irrigation communities, which are not always receptive to this practice.</p> <p>This is the situation in which this success story arises. The San Isidro Salvador de Canena Cooperative (from now on San Isidro Cooperative or the cooperative) began to have difficulties managing its washing water and vegetable water remains during the 90s. In</p>

The Success Story Profile

2000 they implemented a system for collecting wastewater from olive washing and hoppers leakage and built an evaporation pond. The water was dispersed with sprinklers to accelerate its evaporation. It was further promoted by orientating the sprinkle jet towards the slopes at the sides of the pond, which reached high temperature during the day as they were covered with a dark tarp.

During the following years, they kept looking for alternative solutions able to reduce the energy cost of the evaporating pond. The cooperative started contacting the nearby irrigation communities and carried out individual short irrigation tests with this wastewater. It was then detected that this practice generated obstructions in some irrigation systems. This reinforced the reluctance and worries of part of the irrigation communities as this practice could damage their irrigation systems.

The success story began to take shape in 2010, when the San Isidro Cooperative installed an automatic filtering system before sending the water to the ponds. To this end, the cooperative looked for possible solutions, and found AZUD, a specialised company that provided the technical solution. They opted to be more exigent than the current filtering systems utilised by the local irrigation systems, and installed a robust system (disc filter AZUD Helix Automatic) designed to eliminate solid matter larger than 100µm.

Thanks to this equipment, it was possible to reduce the deposits that remained in the pond after evaporation, and reduce operation and maintenance costs of the pond. But additionally, this small innovation opened the doors to take the next step, since the filtered water was, due to its technical specifications, suitable in terms of suspended solids, for irrigation systems already in place in the area.

It was in 2011 when the San Isidro Cooperative proposed to the irrigation community Corral Rubio de las Grullas to introduce pre-treated olive washing wastewater into its irrigation network. The cooperative provided the technical data on the quality of the treated water, and the General Assembly of the irrigation community accepted. The decision making was motivated by three factors, all of them related to confidence: (1) a large part of the members of the irrigation community were members of the cooperative; (2) the objective data on treated water quality (in terms of suspended solid matter); and (3) the fact that the San Isidro cooperative compromised to amend any damage that the washing water could cause in the irrigation network of the irrigation community.

On the other hand, the administration strongly supported the project to reuse olive washing water in fertigation because it was a pioneer and solved the problem of managing washing water in oil mills. This helped to obtain the permits, and further supported the decision to the eyes of the members of the irrigation community. After obtaining administrative and environmental permits in 2012, this residual water began to be partially injected into the irrigation network. The strategy was to apply a low dose to promote high dilution to reduce the risk of possible obturations, rather than optimisation and benefit of nutrient contributions.

It is in 2020 when a new step is taken. The experience from the previous years was satisfactory in terms the practice did not cause any damage in the irrigation systems. But the irrigators (farmers) and the cooperative lacked data on how the fertigation was improving or retaining crops growth. Farmers, being increasingly aware of climate change and the effects of droughts, and with more pressure on their production costs, started considering investing in more efficient irrigation systems such as precision subsurface irrigation. There arises the question of the compatibility of these precision systems, the

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>appropriate doses, and the nutritional effects, which could lead farmers to reduce needs on fertilisers.</p> <p>Following the relationship of trust established between the San Isidro cooperative and the technological facilitator AZUD, it promoted the constitution of the SUBALMA EIP-AGRI operational group (EFARD funding) to evaluate the compatibility of fertigation with olive washing water in underground irrigation. The project is financed, and begins in January 2021, joining the interests of 6 entities: the cooperative as a receiving agent of innovation, AZUD as a technological facilitator, the CEBAS-CSIC as an R&D center in order to monitor the effect of irrigation, the consulting firm EVERGRANT and ASAJA JAÉN farmers organisation for the transfer of results to the sector, and the Jaén Province local government (deputation) as accompanying and supervisory entity.</p> <p>Through the project, it was aimed to adapt the wastewater to subsurface irrigation systems applied to olive groves, guaranteeing the productivity and the water and nutrient efficiency. But additionally, and as a general objective, the project sought to promote an improvement in the productivity, competitiveness and sustainability of olive and olive oil producers. Therefore it included awareness-raising and transfer actions of the solution adopted.</p> <p>The SUBALMA project closed in 2023, demonstrating and quantifying the positive impact of using olive washing water through precision subsurface fertigation. Among them, it has quantified the cost reduction in wastewater management, it has monitored irrigation systems, confirming the absence of negative effects, and it has demonstrated the increase in the productivity of fruit oil yield in systems with underground fertigation. Furthermore, crop monitoring indicated the absence of negative effects for the crop itself.</p> <p>Link to SUBALMA project.</p> <p>https://biorural-toolkit.eu/research-projects/?id=784</p> <p>https://www.subalma.com/</p>
The team behind the story	<p>The partners promoting the innovation have been firstly, the agricultural Cooperative San Isidro Labrador de Canena (in Jaén Province), which envisioned the possibility to convert their problem with the washing wastewater into an opportunity. As well the local farmers irrigation community Corral Rubio de las Grullas, who was the user of the wastewater. AZUD as facilitator of the technical innovation played a role not only to provide the solution, but to create confidence on the quality of the waste water and its compatibility with the irrigation systems in place.</p> <p>In a second stage, an Operational Group of the EIP AGRI is triggered to go beyond, and quantify the positive effects of the system, then participated by several organisations. Crucial for this group to trigger effects in replication is the participation of ASAJA Jaén farmers organisation and the Jaén province government Deputation. The knowledge based evidence was reached by a R&D organisation (CEBAS-CSIC national research organisation).</p>
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>Adopters of the wastewater treatment: olive olive mills and olive cooperatives.</p> <p>Potential adopters of the irrigation water, and of the adapted subsurface irrigation nozzles are olive irrigation communities, farmers and farmers cooperatives.</p> <p>Key partners are those facilitating the technical solution (irrigation companies e.g. AZUD company)</p>

The Success Story Profile	
Vision and Future plans	The success case has demonstrated the compatibility of the wastewater from olive washing for fertigation. After the innovation project SUBALMA finished, the cooperative has continued offering the washing wastewater to farmers. Several have started using it though superficial drip irrigation, which is easier in terms of supply and entails much lower risk for obturation. New users using subsurface irrigation, beyond the already established pilot field, are expected to multiply. Furthermore the multiplying effect of ASAJA and the Jaén Province deputation are expected to trigger replication in the area.

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2000	The cooperative installs the sprinkling system to evaporate olive washing wastewater
2	2001-2010	The cooperative starts contacts with local irrigation communities in order to introduce wastewater into the local irrigation systems. Trials and error assays with wastewater in the local irrigation systems.
3	2010	The cooperative installs a filtering system able to produce a treated water compatible with irrigators community demand
4	2011	The general Assembly of one of the local irrigation communities (Corral Rubio de las Grullas irrigators) agrees to use the water in their irrigation systems.
5	2021	A EIP Agri Operational SUBALMA group is triggered, including also local authorities and farmers associations, to obtain quantified data on the practice, and to further extend this practice to other irrigation systems and to other geographical areas
6	2023	The SUBALMA project finishes and becomes one of the 30 nominated to the Agricultural & Rural Inspiration Awards (ARIA) 2023

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	It involves the cooperative, and olive farmers next to it, who can use the washing wastewater and nutrients. It promotes local circularity of 2 valuable resources: water and nutrients.
team and network	5	It involves the interest of 300 local farmers of the cooperative. It also has triggered the interest of regional farmers organisation and authorities. Additionally, it involved the capacities of a technology facilitator, a specialised consultant and a scientific organisation.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	The problem to be tackled is relevant for the cooperative, and the solution is straight. It also improves resilience of olive groves to water and nutrient stress, whilst solving the management of wastewater, which implied costs.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	5	Trial and error tests were performed from 2001 onwards, and it was evidenced wastewater was not compatible with local irrigation systems, thus indicating a treatment was necessary. In 2011 the use of filtered wastewater starts, and no damage is observed during 9 years of observation. The participants however, want to go beyond and learn what is the quantification of the positive or negative effects of this practice, and a collaborative innovation action is triggered in 2021, a EIP-Agri Operational Group. It allows to obtain evidence based data useful to trigger replication and to extend the practice to other areas and to other irrigation systems.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
financial sustainability	4	<p>Adopting the practice involves an initial investment by the cooperatives or olive mills, who are the actors having to deal with the wastewater problem. This solves the issue to inject the treated water in the irrigation network.</p> <p>The farmers equipped with drip surface irrigation systems can already adopt the water. For subsurface systems farmers need to include special water diffusers (nozzles). This is a barrier for pre-existing subsurface systems, which costs for replacing nozzles imply relevant costs. The cost is not so differential for those farmers investing in new facilities.</p>
social cohesion	5	<p>The system does not create any problems for the community. It resolves a problem for the cooperative, and creates a chance for collaboration among farmers. It is precise to create confidence and mutual understanding between olive mills / cooperatives and local irrigators communities. Also with local permitting authorities. Therefore adopting the practice triggers a process of cohesion and understanding.</p>

To be successful, the story required creation of confidence between the actors involved in the new circular bioeconomy practice. Providing objective data on the quality of the by-product to be utilised was crucial (water quality parameters). And to expand to other areas, an innovation action that is able to quantify benefits has been crucial.

5.1.1.2 Conclusion

The bio-based solution initiated by the San Isidro Salvador de Canena Cooperative, in order to efficiently manage olive washing wastewater results in a wide range of positive effects, from the management of the waste stream itself, to the water and cost savings, as well as the recycling of nutrients, addressing multiple challenges/needs in the area where this solution is implemented. Moreover, as mentioned above, this success story highlights some important aspects to be taken into account towards the adoption of circular bioeconomy, including the development of networks and clusters that involve interested parties, transparency regarding the quality of secondary materials, etc.

5.2 Bioeconomy Theme: Forestry

5.2.1 Forest silviculture for fire prevention at ecotourism resort

5.2.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Forest silviculture for fire prevention at ecotourism resort
Subtitle - tagline	The regenerative initiative to prevent from fire and maintain energy self-sufficiency
Bioeconomy theme	Forestry, energy
Core Activities	Tourism, camping, forest silviculture, energy self sufficiency
Full Address	Finca El Tercio Nuevo, s/n, 28739 Gargantilla del Lozoya, Madrid Location: 40.94975, -3.7300
No of employees	25
Funding sources	Forestry operations self-financed

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	Monte Holiday Ecoturismo (MHE) is a pioneering eco-tourism resort combining camping parcels and bungalows in an area of 27 hectares in the mountain range of Sierra de Madrid. The resort owner installed in 2013 a biomass district heating to suffice heat demands from the accommodation facilities. Worried about the potential impact of forest

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>fires in the resort, he developed a self protection plan in 2018 which evidenced the campsite vulnerability to fires due to the accumulation of biomass in the forestry land next by. Starting with a self-protection plan and an update of the forest management plan, thinnings operations were programmed to reduce the forestry density, and to be utilised in the resort as fuel for the heating system. This initiative started in 2023.</p>
Detailed Description	<p>Monte Holliday Ecoturismo (MHE) is a touristic campsite and resort located at 1200 m altitude in a mountainside slope, in the Sierra de Madrid, 80 kilometers North from Madrid city. The mediterranean forest mass around the campsite has been growing for over 50 years given the decay of firewood use and of the animal grazing.</p> <p>This resort has incorporated renewable energies to reduce its carbon footprint and counts on with 99 kW photovoltaics and with a 2 km long district heating system providing hot water and heat to the bungalows and cabins since 2013. This network operated on the base of a boiler fed with high quality dried woodchips.</p> <p>MHE owner was well aware of the increasing risk for forest fires and the fact that an eventual fire could destroy the camping facilities, its natural environment, and be a threat for the life of the users. It was 2018 when the campsite owner, after conversations with family and local inhabitants, decided to take action. Having a background as forest engineer, Antonio Gonzalo (owner) contacted a former professor of the foresters engineering school in Madrid. A short collaboration led to a draft of a risk map, where it was evidenced that the main risk for the camping and users was outside, and not inside it. During next years Antonio matured the self -protection plan and established contacts with some experts and the emergency service of Madrid province.</p> <p>Firemen technicians visiting the resort stated that if a fire starts, it would not stop until reaching the top of the hill. They advised that fires in a mediterranean forest with more than 10 tonnes per hectare of mass are able to generate energy of more than 10,000 kilowatts per meter of fire front. And that above this energy intensity it is basically impossible to extinct it and fight against it.</p> <p>It was evidenced that fire risk was a main threat for the campsite and local environment. The forest next by, owned as well by Antonio Gonzalo, was very closed and accumulated up to 60 or 70 t/ha in some areas after years of no management. The situation in a 30% slope would further create a chimney effect that would propagate the fire till the top of the hill.</p> <p>Following the experts and firemen suggestions Antonio decided to update the forest management plan, with a plan to reduce forest density. To state the need it was first necessary to prepare a self-protection plan, which was developed during 2019 and 2020.</p> <p>A second issue was to manage the forestry debris obtained during the thinning operations. Then Antonio matched the idea. Would it be possible to use the biomass obtained from the forest silvicultural operations to feed the district heating of the campsite? At that moment the energy bill to purchase woodchips reached 20 to 30,000 €/year. Why not invest it into treating the surrounding forests and go ahead with the fire prevention plan?</p> <p>After consulting with specialised companies and boiler manufacturers they recommended installing new boilers, prepared for such fuel. Coming from branches, bushes and thinning of non-commercial trees, it would incorporate species like holm oak, oak, juniper or locust. A shredding process would be necessary, which would produce a heterogeneous</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>wood fuel incorporating also sand and soil particles. A special adapted boiler would be necessary to be installed. This would imply extra investment, but at same time, would help to bring value to the biomass produced, and close the circle locally.</p> <p>2023 MHE owner finished and communicated to the corresponding authority the renewed forest management plan, which included the self protection plan. As well it was communicated to the local municipalities, which once received, had to incorporate it into their own Emergency and Self Protection municipal plans. And the purchase and installation of a new boiler (500 kW mobile grate boiler) took place, implying a new investment of 300, 000 €.</p> <p>The forestry operations concentrated during the first campaign (2022-2023) in the area next to the resort's superior edge, the area of highest priority. The operations were carried out with manual felling with chainsaws, haulage with telehandlers and regular 3 axis trucks. After 3 months the biomass bundles were shredded and converted into a very dry hog fuel with pieces of maximum 12 cm length. This material has been utilised satisfactorily in the boiler since then.</p> <p>The second campaign in 2023-2024 the treatments were carried out in a more complex area. In this case the forestry technique had to adapt to slope, and involved manual felling. Haulage was not carried out, but after 2 months of drying. Then the material is to be gathered and transported out of the forest with a forestry truck (with a self loader). This will allow leaves and twigs to remain in the soil, providing important nutrients on the forest soil (thus contributing to circularity).</p> <p>The economic accounting however does not provide savings in respect to the previous bill of purchase forest woodchips. The first campaign, i.e. the thinning and fuel processing costs were double in comparison with the standard forest woodchips purchase. The second season costs are going above due to the increased difficulty of operation.</p> <p>Notwithstanding, and as explained by Antonio as MHE owner, the most important is the self protection, since a forest fire could endanger the life of persons in the area, and destroy the campsite and local landscape. Investing just some additional money to work in preventing this risk is advantageous, especially once the synergy is established to use the forest residual biomass for the heating network.</p>
The team behind the story	<p>Monte Holiday resort owner, Antonio Gonzalo, who is not only campsite manager but also forest engineer. This was relevant to be able to go ahead with the fire risk prevention plan and with the forest management plan. In other villages, campings, etc. collaboration with forest specialists would be necessary.</p> <p>Collaboration was also established with the University of Madrid (forestry engineers school) to prepare the risk assessment, and with the firemen of the emergency service of Madrid community.</p>
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>Target audience: Village councils in areas of forestry with potential vulnerability to fire risk, campings or housing resorts nearby forestry interface area.</p> <p>Key partners: necessary to collaborate and to be previously aware are environmental offices (permitting authorities), regional forestry planners, local councils.</p>
Vision and Future plans	<p>The next steps will be orientated to adapt the forestry operations to other areas at larger distance and with steeper slopes. This involves opening 2 forest tracks, and ideating methods for the haulage of the forestry biomass debris in the steeper areas.</p>

The Success Story Profile

	Furthermore the utilisation of grazing with cows or goats to reduce new bushes sprouting and preserve forest density is being planned.
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Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2013	Installation of a district heating system with a woodchip biomass boiler
2	2018	Internal discussion with locals about state of forest and need for treatment as being a threat
3	2019-2020	Maturing of the self-protection plan and contact with experts and firemen from the emergency services
4	2022-2023	Preparation of the self-protection plan and update of the forest management plan (submitted to the permitting authority)
5	2023	Installation of the new biomass boiler. Performing first thinning and preparation of biomass batch
6	2023-2024	First operation of the district heating using the biomass from local forests. Starting the second campaign with new forestry operational methods.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	The initiative is totally local. The operations are applied to a local forest mass next to the camping resort. The biomass produced is utilised in the boiler which provides heating service to the camping. The biomass is obtained by means of an updated forest management plan, which incorporates measures to reduce erosion, impact, and nutrients withdrawal.
team and network	4	The head of the initiative has been the key to developing it. It has been a relevant collaboration of the MHE team, together with the University of Madrid forest experts and with firemen of the emergency service of Madrid community. It was however not necessary to group or to put into agreement local stakeholders previously.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	This is applicable to any type of urban-forest interface (e.g. villages, housing areas, a group of houses, a campsite, a rural hotel). This success case exemplifies how to proceed: prepare a self-protection plan to subsequently develop a forest management plan. Then to couple the intervention with the consumption of the biomass produced in an existing or new facility. This is applicable, and is very relevant in Mediterranean forest areas subjected to forest fire risk.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	4	This practice has required testing and collaboration with other companies expert in forest handling. It involved testing of thinning and handling of first batches. And boiler tests. It did not incorporate any R&D project at the moment, but more tests are coming, as the new thinnings have to face more complex operational conditions. The project is replicable, as it does incorporate usual forestry operations. The main issue for replication is to count with local consumers for the biomass produced out of the forest operations.
financial sustainability	4	<p>This practice is not economically driven. It means that the biomass obtained from the thinnings results in double price than a standard high quality wood chip fuel. However, it is an investment to protect local natural habitats, local population and local business.</p> <p>All in all the synergy is beneficial with high added value, though not visible in the economic bill or annual accounting. In some cases it could be explored the possibility of access to subsidies for forestry treatment for prevention. As well once the fire risk has been reduced, companies could revise the insurance conditions, which could reduce the insurance fee.</p>

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
social cohesion	5	Promoting these practices requires dialogue with local councils, firemen or fire prevention services and permitting authorities. Furthermore in areas of multiple private owners, it promotes dialogue and facilitates coordinated action for the benefit of all owners and the local community. Furthermore the local natural resources are protected and vulnerability of local inhabitants is reduced, which is a value to the eyes of local inhabitants. In this case 2 private owners have already collaborated with MHE initiative to also execute fire prevention thinnings in their parcels.

5.2.1.2 Conclusion

The forest silviculture initiative of MHE successfully highlights the importance of sustainable coexistence between humans and nature for the protection of both. MHE's bio-based solution takes into account the threats and opportunities related with the environment surrounding the resort and develops a management plan for the benefit of both the business and the neighboring natural habitats. Notably, the initiative also incorporated circular practices, i.e. valorisation of the residual biomass that comes from silviculture activities to produce energy, and puts emphasis on the indirect costs associated with the possibility of a vast forest fire (i.e. environmental disaster), which are often underestimated.

5.3 Bioeconomy Theme: Aquatic and Water Systems

5.3.1 Aquaponics Iberia

5.3.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Aquaponics Iberia
Subtitle - tagline	Small-scale, closed and dynamic systems combining Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS) with hydroponics techniques, ready for up-scaling
Bioeconomy theme	Water Systems, Food & Agriculture
Core Activities	Aquaculture, Hydroponics, Aquaponics
Full Address	Avenida Tenente Valadim 17, 2º F 2560-275 Torres Vedras
No of employees	5
Funding sources	Bootstrapping, Climate-KIC, RRP voucher for start-ups

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	With its nature-based modular technology, it has hacked the closed-loop balanced aquaponics systems, making it simultaneously long-term productive, cost-efficient, highly safe and sustainable, while growing the best organic tasty fresh food, supplying healthy and sustainable conscious consumers in large cities, in a totally circular and farm-to-fork approach.
Detailed Description	<p>Aquaponics Iberia is a specialised startup in aquaponics, providing consultancy, engineering, systems design, implementation and training.</p> <p>Its team has developed a technology for aquaponics called SWIMS (Solid Waste Integrated Management System) that turns aquaponics simultaneously truly sustainable, organic, highly productive and low maintenance demanding, compared to the current aquaponics state of the art. They have hacked aquaponics systems into a truly circular solution, that takes advantage of their expertise and efficient technology to expand sustainable and local healthy food security in densely populated European regions.</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>Aquaponics Iberia uses a food production technique that combines Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS) with hydroponics techniques (plant cultivation on water), in a closed and dynamic system where fish waste nourishes plants, which in turn purify water for fish to grow healthily.</p> <p>Water is recycled continuously by plants and nutrients are maintained at a constant level, without the need to resort to synthetic fertilisers. Additionally, pesticides for plants or medication for fish cannot be used, as it would negatively affect fish and plants. Furthermore, through a circular approach, duckweed is grown using residual aquaponics organic waste to replace 30% of commercial fish feed. It is a productive symbiotic ecosystem that truly uses organic and environmentally sustainable methodologies and dramatically saves water.</p> <p>Some commercial units using Aquaponics Iberia’s design are already operational in Portugal and in the Caribbean, and pilot-plants are already implemented in two schools, through the project School Farming.</p> <p>Aiming the scale-up of this solution, their Fish n’ Greens project was designed to use their technologies combining nature and innovation and bring the production of the best fresh fish and vegetables to large cities, close to people, in a sustainable, ecological and transparent way, favouring not only freshness and healthy eating, but also integration with local communities through initiatives that raise awareness of environmental education, in particular through guided tours for local schools.</p> <p>This project allows the cultivation of food with virtually no water waste/consumption and no wastewater, without effluent, and supplying local food without long-distance transportation, contributing to a low carbon circular economy.</p>
The team behind the story	<p>Core team constituted by a CEO with +20 years of experience in aquaculture & aquaponics, a COO with +40 years of experience in aquaculture & aquaponics, a CCO with +10 years of experience in sales, food safety & processing, and a CSO with +17 years of experience in marine biology & aquatic R&D.</p> <p>Finance and business development team constituted by a banking management & financial markets expert, with +20 years of experience in the banking industry focusing on financing companies and projects, and a finance & international business expert with +30 years of experience in global industry sectors, such as life sciences, real estate acquisitions, asset management, hospitality, media and entertainment, and executive training.</p>
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>End-users of the solution: Landowners, farmers, real-estate investors, schools and universities, hotels, municipalities – for consultancy services and aquaponics systems Additionally, general public – for training</p> <p>Aquaponics products consumers: Restaurants, hotels, food retailers, municipal school canteens (B2B), End-consumers (B2C)</p> <p>Key partners: municipalities, universities and research institutes, colabs, associations, fish feed manufacturers, sustainable fresh food packaging companies, and food retailers.</p>
Vision and Future plans	<p>Build the first Fish n’ Greens commercial unit during 2024, and later, replicate it in other cities with a 5 units goal for 2030 (3 in Portugal and 2 abroad)</p> <p>Through the project School Farming (Educational Aquaponics for Schools), the company intends to involve 20 schools until 2025, installing aquaponics systems for educational</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	purposes, involving the school community including students, teachers, and parents to create better education, a better food system and a better environment.

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	May 2016	Organisation of a successful international workshop on aquaponics
2	February 2017	Company incorporated
3	January 2018	First operational commercial aquaponics system in Portugal
4	December 2018	Other commercial units in the Caribbean
5	January 2019	SWIMS Technology demonstrated and validated through aquaponics systems' clients
6	Now	Fish n' Greens project is investment-ready (technology, legal framework, business model, partnerships), although still working on fund raising

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	4	Food production and supply intended for local markets and consumers (urban farming); through a circular approach, grow duckweed using residual aquaponics organic waste to replace 30% of commercial fish feed.
team and network	5	Interdisciplinary team; local partnerships (municipality, university, colabs, associations).
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	Sustainable solution for the food system: extreme circularity, low water use and waste, less inputs of feed, fertilisers and energy, and high quality natural food products. Demonstrated and validated technology.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	5	The solution is now at TRL 8, several pilots were implemented at lab level, as well as operational environment level. Some commercial units were implemented, demonstrating and validating the technology. Now, the technology is still missing a large-scale commercial stage (economies of scale, i. e. replicating production modules in a single facility).
financial sustainability	4	At full-scale - Project Fish n' Greens financial projections (one unit): 44% ROI average per year, 61% EBITDA-To-Sales Ratio, 3-year Payback. 35% of the required funding for the first unit is already secured through investment funds.
social cohesion	5	Food and environmental education and awareness through an aquaponics project for schools, in partnership with IPMA (sea and atmosphere institute), Smart Farm Colab, Aquário Vasco da Gama (public aquarium). Educational guided tours for commercial aquaponics systems (Fish n' Greens) and supplying fresh fish and vegetables to local school canteens.

Relevant links

1. <https://www.aquaponicsiberia.com/>
2. <https://www.fishngreens.eu/2024-updated/>

5.3.1.2 Conclusion

Aquaponics Iberia activities promote sustainable, circular and resilient food systems that may be established in the urban environment, contributing to large cities food safety, in terms of food production and food quality. They offer a replicable bio-based solution, while also consulting and training interested parties and communities, so as to raise awareness and transfer knowledge, which are important for the wider acceptance and adoption of such solutions. At the same time, Aquaponics Iberia puts emphasis on research and development through

relevant projects, in order to continuously improve the quality of the circularity and sustainability of their aquaponic systems and practices.

5.4 Bioeconomy Theme: Biomaterials and Bioproducts

5.4.1 Innovative biostimulants and plant protection bioproducts from wood residues

5.4.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Innovative biostimulants and plant protection bioproducts from wood residues
Subtitle - tagline	BIODea redefine the use of biochar in agriculture
Bioeconomy theme	Biomaterials & Bioproducts
Core Activities	Production of bioproducts from wood
Full Address	Via delle Case Rosse, 22/A, 52040 Tuori, Civitella in Val di Chiana, Arezzo
No of employees	11
Funding sources	Private/internal (self founding)

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	The company internally developed an innovative pyrolysis plant that enables them to produce stable and high quality biochar that is further liquefied with other bioproducts (like algae) based on desired functionality.
Detailed Description	<p>The company was born as a technological industry focused on the development of pyrolysis and gasification plants for a broad variety of residues. At the beginning, the technological development of the plant was aimed at maximizing the electrical energy production through internal combustion of synthesis gasses produced from wood.</p> <p>In Italy these technologies were heavily supported by state aid for a short period, after such a period the companies that start working on the sector have suffered a serious market depression.</p> <p>The company kept going and has revolutionised the plant development aiming at high quality biochar production, the company not only aimed at the development of high quality biochar but also developed a product that is safe for the worker. In fact, by developing a liquid form product the company solved the problems related to the volatile dust generated by BIOchar in the solid form.</p> <p>The product is highly innovative and subsequently the use of such a product has to be innovative in order to be effective on the crop. For that reason the company developed a post sale technical service in order to support their clients.</p> <p>Their clients, mainly farmers specialised in production of wine or olive oil, benefit from a more sustainable product (less chemicals involved) without compromising with quality.</p>
The team behind the story	The team is guided by the CEO (Francesco Barbagli) and is composed of agronomists and mechanical engineers. Interdisciplinary approach to the development of the technology and to the marketing of the products is one of the key strengths of the company.
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	The key clients for the companies are innovative farms focused on sustainable farming and on reducing the use of mineral fertilisers and other chemical products.
Vision and Future plans	The company is ready and is producing innovative fertilisers. The next step comes with the expected growth of the market and consequently the growth of production.

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	1990	The company was born and started developing gasification plant for cogeneration of electricity and heat
2	2016	Failing of the market for gasification technologies in Italy
3	2017	Upgrading of the plant for the stable production of high quality biochar
4	2019	BIODea begin commercializing fertilisers under the Italian fertilisers law
5	2020	BIODea developed a biochar fertiliser in liquid form
6	2021	Europe finally recognise biochar as a constituent for fertilisers
7	2022	BioDea brand develops of over 10 natural and organic products catalog
8	2024	In line with the European objectives of substitution of toxic plant protection products., BioDea begins the production of formulations for new products for sustainable agriculture

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	The products developed help farmers to replace chemicals or mineral products that often are imported from extra European countries.
team and network	5	One of the strengths of the company is the services they deliver to their customers, they not only offer biochar but also technical after sale support to the companies in order to properly use the product in order to be effective.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	3	The effectiveness of the product for the intended use is proven by an extensive bibliography although the price for the intended use is slightly higher than mineral/fossil alternatives. Furthermore, in order to be effective, farmers need to re-think the approach to treatments and fertilisations.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	2	The market for biochar is still a niche market and there are only a few technologies on the market that allow the production of high quality biochar.
financial sustainability	3	Despite the success of the company, thanks to an excellent work on marketing their product, biochar and biochar derived products cover a niche market in the sector of fertilisers and plant biostimulants.
social cohesion	4	The use of biochemicals and the short supply chain brings benefits to the local community, both economical and environmental. However the acceptance of small scale biorefineries is still affected by the misinformation of local communities that are generally afraid of any in process they cannot understand well (NIMBY syndrome).

5.4.1.2 Conclusion

BIODea contributes to the promotion of circular bioeconomy not only by producing innovative fertilisers to replace chemical products using (wood) waste as raw material, but also by properly informing and supporting target audiences to effectively use these products. Moreover, this success story showcases the importance for businesses to be updated regarding policies and relevant provisions, as well as to invest on innovation and modification of production lines, since these are factors that may contribute to business resilience and development.

5.5 Bioeconomy Theme: Bioenergy

5.5.1 Cooperative composting and biogas energy production

5.5.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Cooperative composting and biogas production
Subtitle - tagline	Solving the management of pig and cattle slurry and manure by cooperation of 150 families of farmers
Bioeconomy theme	Bioenergy, Biomaterials & Bioproducts
Core Activities	Creation of a governance structure joining interests of 150 farmers families. Designation of volunteered farmers to lead the search for solutions. Creation of a modern composting plant and a new biogas plant.
Full Address	polygon 11 parcel 62-64, 25180 Alcarràs, Lleida Coordinates: 41.5954, 0.4021
No of employees	6 full time employees
Funding sources	The composting plant investment required 1.5 M€ and the biogas plant required an investment of 2.5 M€. Both have been invested without any subsidy support. These steps are the path towards the creation of a local biohub.

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	150 families of pig and cattle breeding and fattening small farms joined efforts since 2006 to collectively manage the manure generated in Alcarràs municipality. Its management was a common issue for all, and aggregation allowed them to invest in a medium scaled solution consisting of a composting and a biogas plant, first step to establish a local biohub.
Detailed Description	<p>Alcarràs is one of the municipalities in Europe with higher density of livestock production with a population of 250,000 pig for fattening, 55,000 swine for breeding, and 70,000 cattle, generating more than 300,000 m³ of slurry and 250,000 t of manure per year.</p> <p>The as usual practice was the use of both slurry and manure as soil amendment, but the legal conditions and high quantities were causing local farms to undergo stress and higher costs for its management.</p> <p>It was already since 2006 that several local farms started looking for solutions. Then they stated the difficulties of adopting individual solutions, and started a process to join forces between the two local pig and cattle farmers associations.</p> <p>From the beginning a specialised engineering company was contracted to help envision the potential solutions, starting from manure and pig slurry characterisation, and to identify scaled solutions. About 2010 a group of farmers, about 8, representing both farmers organisations, were designated to steer the process. This committee met, discussed, and proposed solutions to the assembly of each organisation. They realised composting and biogas production could be the solution.</p> <p>The farmers association started to also involve the local governments of the 8 local municipalities concerned. A climate of cooperation and understanding was created, and several small projects for promotion were launched, as for example Green&Circular initiative of territorial development. This helped to start visiting other biohubs in Europe hand in hand with the municipalities.</p>

The Success Story Profile

In 2019 the SAT Alcarràs Bioproductors was created to implement a cooperative composting plant. A surface of 17ha of fields was acquired and the construction of the composting plant started 2022, with a capacity to treat 27,000 t/year of solid fraction of pig and cattle slurry and manure.

The value chain starts at the farms, with the separation of manure to solid and liquid fraction farm by farm. Farmers keep the liquid fraction, to be utilised as additive to irrigation in local fields, whereas the solid fraction is sent to the composting plant. A transport company hired to collect the solid fraction under farmers demand, and bring it to the treatment plant in Alcarràs. The transport fee is the same for all farmers, regardless of the distance from the processing plant.

The solid fraction of manure gets mixed with the biomass (principally from parks and gardens, but also from pruning and other woody biomass).

The composting process is actively aerated with forced air fed from air nodes in narrow channels in the paved soil: the piles base on a layer of thick pieces of wood to avoid clogging of air nozzles, and the manure and wood mixture is then piled on it, including temperature and moisture control. Once the process is finished, the compost is screened in a rotary drum, the fine fraction to become the final product, and the thick part to be recovered and included as new material with the fresh batches.

The regular compost is sold to local farms, whereas the best products, which are suitable for organic production, find a market of higher value both in Spain and France (given the relatively short distance to the French border). Given the good results in 2023 the SAT Alcarràs started the expansion of the composting capacity, to be able to handle 54,000 t/year.

Furthermore the SAT Alcarràs Bioproductors is installing a biogas plant with the aim to start producing bioenergy, both thermal and electric. The cooperative has established a new energy community, turning farmers into energy prosumers. The plant consists of 2 biodigesters of 3,600 m³ and implies an investment of 2.5 M€. It is expected to treat 63,000 m³ of slurry and 7,000 t of manure directly to produce more than 1.7 million cubic meters of biogas. The electricity generated will be utilised for self-consumption in the composting plant (circa 100 kW), and to the electricity network (265 kW). Heat will be utilised partly for the composting plant, intended to be extended for heating to nearby farms, and to supply heat to a new agri-food facility to be installed next to the biogas and composting plant.

The SAT Alcarràs Bioproductors story shows the path for social innovation, where not only technical solutions, but adapted and needed solutions of interest for all are adopted. The design of the facilities has been based on knowledge gained and on own creative contributions, also counting with experts and scientists, not just the purchase of a turkey solution. The solution enables circularity for residues, producing high added value commodities like biogas and compost, and reducing the impact of manure in the area.

The team behind the story

The story relies on the aggregation of interest of 2 local farmers associations. The participation of volunteer farmers who led the ideation of the initiative (representing 150 families of farmers) was a key factor.

Eight local municipalities have participated since 2018 in promotional actions, to promote a biohub at the service of all. University of Lleida and other research actors have also added vision and solutions in the mature stage of the initiative. Lastly the local province

The Success Story Profile	
	government (Deputation of Lleida province) has included this initiative as ones of the territorial strategic projects (BiohubCat km0), thus providing official backup.
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	Breeding and fattening pig and/or cattle farms Key partners have been local municipalities and the Lleida local government who supported the initiative and facilitated partial funding as a regional strategic project.
Vision and Future plans	The path to the future started right after composting plant commissioning in 2023, investing in its expansion and the biogas plant. It is also expected to include in future a process to denitrify the liquid fractions of digestate, to obtain ammonium sulphate and a clarified stable digestate for irrigation. Furthermore, the plan is to install an agri-food industry, to produce vegetal protein. The biogas waste heat will be utilised for processing, and the protein will be for self consumption by the cooperative farms. It is also intended to explore the possibility to upgrade biogas to biomethane to inject it directly in the gas network.

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2006	Local farmers start dialogue to find solutions for management of pig and cattle manure and slurry. The 2 farmers organisations (150 families) start joining forces.
2	2007	Farmers organisations decide to hire services of an expert engineering company to gain knowledge and vision.
3	2010	The farmers organisations create a committee of persons to lead the active search for solutions. Regular meetings take place, as well as visits to providers and ongoing facilities, and dialogue with local authorities.
4	2018	Alcarrás Bioproductors SAT is Created
5	2019	Several promotional actions take place with local authorities to create a local solution for all municipality organic residues, thus creating social cohesion.
6	2022	Composting plant starts operation in early 2022 and is inaugurated June 2022 officially
7	2023	Bioenergy community is created and the biogas plant starts construction.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	The action is oriented to handle local manure and slurry, by local farmers.
team and network	5	The initiative started by aggregating the interests of 150 families of pig and cattle farmers. Fer farmers were designated to lead the search for solutions. They interacted with the local research community, consultants, and technology providers. Alcarás Bioproductors SAT became the base for BiohubCat km0 transformation project, including actors of quadruple helix.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	The solution resolves an important issue for the farmers and for the local environment and inhabitants. The composting and biogas plant allows to treat the manure and slurry, reducing risk of nitrogen contamination of soil and underground water reservoirs. It further reduces odours of application of fresh manure/slurry in agricultural land.
Testing & piloting-	4	The testing and piloting was not carried in situ. The solution for composting and biogas relied on previous success cases that farmers visited. The manure and slurry were characterised in collaboration with a local research organisation. Replicability is

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
scalability & replicability		possible, though the most difficult is the aggregation of small farms to scale-up the size of the initiative.
financial sustainability	5	The action can be replicated without need of funding. This initiative would have gone ahead without. Notwithstanding the favourable framework of authorities and small subsidising has accelerated the decision making.
social cohesion	5	It has created cohesion by bringing together in a sole initiative 150 individual family farms. But furthermore several years of dialogue have brought public and private actors to collaborate, and establish common vision and unified promotional actions. No social reactions have occurred thanks to this bottom up process, since local inhabitants have understood the project, and because the process is observed as good for all, not just for farmers, or not just linked to specific party interests.

5.5.1.2 Conclusion

The cooperative composting and biogas production in Alcarrás municipality implemented by the SAT Alcarrás Bioproductors is an excellent paradigm of circular bioeconomy application to sustainably manage a waste stream via proper treatment to produce valuable materials and energy, closing the circle at a local scale. One of the features of this endeavour is to produce energy from renewable resources to provide both for the needs of the cooperative's facilities and for the needs of the local community. A very interesting outcome of this project is that a bottom-up initiative leveraged positive environmental and social changes, including promoting awareness and engagement among stakeholders, boosting the creation of networks towards the accomplishment of a common purpose, etc.

6 Identified Success Stories: South-East RBP

The section presents the identified success stories of the South-East RBP, including Greece, Slovenia, North Macedonia and Romania and represented in the project by IBO, CPERI, ICO, reframe.food, GGP, UL, Algen and Green Energy Cluster. The South-East RBP have already reached the KPI, since they have identified one success story per bioeconomy theme, while they have identified two success stories falling within the “Food and Agriculture” category.

6.1 Bioeconomy Theme: Food & Agriculture

6.1.1 ŽIPO Lenart d.o.o.

6.1.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	ŽIPO Lenart d.o.o.
Subtitle - tagline	Animal husbandry & Arable farming
Bioeconomy theme	Food & Agriculture
Core Activities	Livestock farming, agriculture, logging, warehousing, straw-cutting, insect bio-conversion, photovoltaics
Full Address	Šetarova 21, 2230 Lenart v Slovenskih Goricah.
No of employees	25
Funding sources	Private, government subsidies

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	Implementing and developing the latest technologies in agriculture, efficient use of all side streams, almost zero waste and high self-sustainable.
Detailed Description	<p>ŽIPO Lenart d.o.o., a company primarily engaged in agriculture, reflects the characteristic Slovenian agricultural landscape's fragmentation and faces the challenges common to Slovenian farming. The firm operates across 870 hectares of agricultural land.</p> <p>A significant aspect of the company's operations is the breeding of young beef cattle, conducted at two separate locations. The Šetarova facility houses five barns with a capacity for 650 animals. Another facility in Spodnje Verjane, comprises three barns accommodating 750 cattle. ŽIPO Lenart is recognised as a "second recognised breeding organisation in animal husbandry," engaging in the progeny testing of young bulls of the Simmental breed, focusing on their growth and slaughter qualities exclusively using Slovenian calves.</p> <p>The company has modernised its grain production and storage capabilities with a state-of-the-art drying and storage facility that leverages green energy innovations for sustainable agricultural development. This investment is aimed at improving the company's competitive position, accessing new markets, and contributing positively to the environment and local agriculture by adding value to their and other farms' agricultural products.</p> <p>ŽIPO Lenart diversified into renewable energy through the investment in solar power, installing four solar power plants with a total capacity of 190 kW on the barn roofs in Šetarova. This move towards renewable energy sources aligns with the global effort to reduce fossil fuel consumption and protect the environment.</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>The company also offers chopped and dust-free straw as bedding for cattle, poultry, and horses, enhancing its absorbency and reducing the amount needed compared to conventional straw. They created their own trademark and patented their process https://www.lenabox.com/. Chopped and dust-free straw is also part of Žipo's feed mix (Lenamix) for calves, where it contributes to proper rumen development as a fibrous component.</p> <p>Research and development are pivotal to ŽIPO Lenart's strategy, leading to the formation of a dedicated team that collaborates in many development and research projects and uses networking with other professional, scientific and research bodies (faculties, institutes, companies, etc.). The company has successfully implemented and commercialised several research projects, including the reduction of pesticides and mineral fertilisers in crop production, the use of alternative methods for weed control, the use of different plant varieties and specially treated seeds (plasma treatment) to improve their emergence, growth and development. Žipo Lenart collaborates with the Faculty of Agriculture and Biosystem Sciences of the University of Maribor. This collaboration spans progeny testing for the Simmental breed, studies on feed additives for beef cattle, and the examination of different forage crops on various soil types to optimise feed rations and ensure sustainable production.</p> <p>Recognizing the growing global demand for animal protein, ŽIPO Lenart has ventured into insect bioconversion as a sustainable alternative for protein production. Since early 2022, the company has been exploring the cultivation of insects for human and animal consumption, dedicating efforts to establish a safe, controlled breeding environment, developing optimal feeding substrates, and extracting proteins from insects.</p>
The team behind the story	<p>The ŽIPO Lenart team consists of several researchers and experts. The head of research and all activities is director Mitja Krajnc, who has a doctorate in mechanical engineering and more than 20 years of experience in agriculture. Other members of the Žipo team are a technologist and two researchers, all of whom have a degree in agriculture or life sciences. They are responsible for all agricultural activities around the field and conducting research. Our member is also the head of the marketing department (economist) and takes care of the financial part of all operations. In addition, part of our team is responsible for administrative tasks. All other ŽIPO members have experience in agriculture, mechanical engineering, harvesting methods, precise agricultural methods (sowing, fertilizing, spraying), management of agricultural vehicles, equipment and production lines. There are 21 people in total.</p>
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>Our main partners are many professional, scientific and research-oriented national institutions (faculties, institutes, agricultural advisory services, companies, etc.). However, ŽIPO also cooperates a lot with local farmers and agricultural enterprises (mutual provision of raw materials, offer of drying and storage services). In addition, ŽIPO has recently started working with ITC companies that offer us intelligent automated solutions. In terms of machinery, agricultural and technological solutions, Žipo cooperates a lot with various service and consulting companies from neighboring countries. Our colleagues, partners and clients form a large interdisciplinary group. Success is the result of combining the strengths, knowledge and skills of everyone involved - each contributing their part to the whole.</p>
Vision and Future plans	<p>In the future, ŽIPO wants to do even more to protect the environment and reuse various raw materials. We will promote the use of renewable energy sources and strive for a circular economy. In agriculture, ŽIPO wants to use even more advanced technologies that enable more environmentally friendly production of safe and high-quality food, animal husbandry and conservation of natural resources. We are planning to introduce new,</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	alternative sources of protein production that are gentler on nature than conventional sources. To summarise, ŽIPO wants to further develop its partnerships and expand its research group. There are no limits to the agricultural areas we can explore, but we focus on efficient and alternative agricultural methods for healthy and safe food production that help protect the environment.

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	Until 1983	The beginnings of the business were born on a traditional medium-sized family farm.
2	1983	Upgrading a farm to a sole proprietorship (construction and agricultural machinery services).
3	2007	Establishment of KGS Krajnc d.o.o. (construction activities to be expanded).
4	2007-2012	Strengthening of agricultural machinery services and extension of activities in the field of wood fuel production (beech wood, wood chips).
5	2012	The agricultural company ŽIPO Živinoreja in poljedelstvo Lenart d.o.o. joins the group.
6	2015	Production of milled and pollinated straw in bales under the Lenabox own brand is launched
7	2019-2021	Receipt of PEFC Chain of Custody certification, Expansion of production with special compound feed under own brand Lenamix

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	All their resources are available in their region
team and network	5	Their team and networks are strong, open-minded, collaborating with many local and global partners.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	They use all of their resources and side-streams, except what the wind blows away
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	4	All of their operations are scalable to a certain point, regarding their resources. Some of them are protected by a patent.
financial sustainability	5	ŽIPO is financially sustainable. Its research and investments are largely based on its own resources. In addition, its products have been on the market for several years and have achieved good sales both at home and abroad.
social cohesion	4	They play a vital role in their environment, providing locals with food and services for local farmers.

Relevant links

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0aDkmTeSF2o>

6.1.1.2 Conclusion

Overall, ŽIPO Lenart d.o.o. constitutes a success story based on shifting from conventional agricultural methods to the adoption of circular and environmentally friendly bio-based solutions throughout the whole production scheme, aiming at the optimisation of both the quality of production and the business’s environmental impact. In house management of byproducts, utilisation of renewable energy resources and the use of natural raw materials rather than chemicals, and sharing infrastructures with nearby farmers are some of the circular practices that make this bio-based solution successful. Last but not least, the development of a strong interdisciplinary

collaboration network to continuously innovate and improve the methods used are a remarkable feature of ŽIPO's activities.

6.1.2 AgFutura Technologies

6.1.2.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	AgFutura Technologies
Subtitle - tagline	Digital and precision agriculture
Bioeconomy theme	Food and agriculture
Core Activities	Implementation of state of the art technologies in the field of agriculture
Full Address	Jurij Gagarin 45/1-1, 1000 Skopje, Republic of North Macedonia
No of employees	12 Full time employees
Funding sources	Boorstrapping, EU and local funded projects

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	Supporting the agricultural sector with innovative solutions in the field of digital and precision agriculture, agri-business development and international agricultural development.
Detailed Description	<p>Digital agriculture</p> <p>Capacity assessment for implementation of DT, Implementation of DT (satellite and UAV monitoring, weather stations, IoT sensors, GPS and VRT equipment, pest and disease modeling software, GIS software, image processing software), education for implementation of DT.</p> <p>Agronomy</p> <p>Soil health, remediation of contaminated soil, plant health and nutrition, bio-based fertilisers, carbon footprint from agriculture, VRT prescriptions, soil conservation and regeneration, IPM, mitigation of climate change effects in production systems, smart irrigation.</p> <p>Digital agriculture promotes environmental sustainability by enabling precision resource management, reducing chemical inputs, conserving biodiversity, lowering greenhouse gas emissions through optimised machinery operations and carbon sequestration, improving land use efficiency, fostering transparent supply chains, and aiding adaptation to climate change.</p>
The team behind the story	A team of 12 full-time and 10 external experts, a total of 22, from different areas such as agricultural engineers, IT experts, economy and business development experts, environmental engineers etc.
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	Farmers/Progressive farmers with knowledge about the benefits of implementation of digital and precision technologies in agriculture / Technology providers, research and academia
Vision and Future plans	AgFutura Technologies continues with its efforts in improving its knowledge, skills, processes and their network of experts in order to provide better and continuous support for our clients in the agro – food industry, in a way that precision and edge-theologies are paramount.

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2016	Foundation of AgFutura Technologies
2	2020	Launch of RAMAS - Remote Agricultural Monitoring and Advisory System
3	2023	Establishment of the Alliance for Digital Transition in Agriculture and Food Industry

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	The needed resources are available in the country and the region.
team and network	5	AgFutura`s team of experts from various areas is capable of development and implementation of these technologies.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	These technologies are effective, highly applicable and with great relevance emerging from their application.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	5	These technologies can be replicated and utilised regardless of location but of course with the need of adaptation to all the variable factors.
financial sustainability	-	-
social cohesion	5	The adoption of these technologies brings together actors from a vast variety of different areas.

Relevant links

1. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q2302eZQos0>
2. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WcufnKlBfpl>
3. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hp8EVDHoHPw>

6.1.2.2 Conclusion

AgFutura Technologies facilitates the transition to more circular and resilient agricultural activities, by means of resource efficiency, climate change adaptation and minimisation of negative environmental impacts, among others, via digitalisation, equipment, consulting and capacity building. Innovation and state of the art technologies are at the core of this success story that aspires to boost the sustainability of rural bioeconomy.

6.2 Bioeconomy Theme: Forestry

6.2.1 OXYGEN OF AGRAFA Social Cooperative Enterprise of Collective and Social Benefit (Koin.S.Ep.)

6.2.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	OXYGEN OF AGRAFA Social Cooperative Enterprise of Collective and Social Benefit (Koin.S.Ep.)
Subtitle - tagline	Oxygen of Agrafa
Bioeconomy theme	Forestry
Core Activities	"Oxygen of Agrafa" Koin.S.Ep. promotes mild forms of tourism, protects, and restores the natural environment and biodiversity, and maintains and enhances hiking, climbing, and cycling paths. The cooperative also organises cultural, sports, and environmental events

General Information	
	and runs information and awareness campaigns focused on environmental protection, biodiversity, and the preservation of cultural and environmental heritage.
Full Address	COMPANY HEADQUARTERS: Neraida Municipality of Plastira Karditsa, 43067 OFFICES: Ypsilantou 50 Karditsa, 43132 WAREHOUSE: El. Venizelou 36, Karditsa, 43100 Tel. 6973695595, 6934770763, 6977394752
No of employees	6
Funding sources	self-sustainable, contracts with public bodies, national or European programmes

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	"Oxygen of Agrafa" focuses on maintaining, restoring, and marking hiking trails. The cooperative aims to revive trails used historically by locals and livestock farmers, encouraging thousands of people from Greece and beyond to explore these paths. They also aim to revitalise trails that connect mountain monasteries, fostering religious tourism combined with hiking and mountaineering tourism. Restoration techniques respect the environment and local microclimates, often involving local community knowledge to preserve and pass down traditional trail usage.
Detailed Description	<p>Oxygen of Agrafa is a vibrant Social Cooperative Enterprise that merges sustainable forestry management with community development. As a forestry bio-based solution, it focuses on preserving, restoring, and promoting hiking trails within the lush forests of the Agrafa region, rich in biodiversity and cultural heritage.</p> <p>The cooperative's main activities involve the maintenance and marking of historical trails, making them accessible and safe for hikers. By revitalizing these paths, Oxygen of Agrafa supports eco-friendly tourism, attracting nature lovers from Greece and beyond, while conserving local forests and ecosystems. Central to their approach is the use of local resources and community participation. The cooperative leverages traditional knowledge and skills from residents for trail restoration, creating jobs and fostering a sense of ownership and pride in the local environment.</p> <p>Oxygen of Agrafa's initiatives embody circular economy principles. By promoting sustainable tourism like hiking, climbing, and cycling, they minimise environmental impact and ensure the sustainable use of forest resources. Restoration techniques are designed to respect local microclimates, and educational campaigns raise awareness about biodiversity and sustainable forestry. Beyond trail work, the cooperative organises cultural and environmental events to highlight Agrafa's natural and cultural heritage. Their proposal for certifying local agri-food products aims to further integrate circular economy principles into their operations.</p> <p>Oxygen of Agrafa is a forestry bio-based solution that combines environmental conservation with social and economic benefits. Their innovative and circular approach to tourism and forestry management serves as a model for similar rural initiatives across Europe.</p>
The team behind the story	In 2019, the love for the mountain prompted a group of Karditsa residents who are governed by the same passion for mountain hiking routes to create the "Oxygen of Agrafa" a Social Cooperative Enterprise, of collective and social benefit with the main purpose of sustainable development in the context of the social and solidarity economy. A group of people with a love for the mountain and their vision to highlight the remarkable

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>ancient, abandoned paths, in Pindos and Agrafa. Paths that were built with pains and on them an important chapter of Greek history was carved.</p> <p>The majority of the group are climbers.</p>
<p>Target audience / Key client / Key partners</p>	<p>Target Audience / Key Client:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Local and International Tourists: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Individuals and groups interested in hiking, climbing, and cycling. b. Nature enthusiasts seeking eco-friendly and sustainable tourism options. c. Religious tourists interested in exploring the historical mountain monasteries. 2. Local Communities: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Residents of Karditsa and the surrounding areas who benefit from improved infrastructure and increased tourism. b. Livestock farmers and other locals who historically used the trails and can contribute to and benefit from their restoration. 3. Environmental and Cultural Organisations: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. NGOs and groups focused on environmental conservation, biodiversity, and cultural heritage preservation. b. Educational institutions and researchers interested in sustainable tourism and environmental studies. 4. Government Bodies and Public Institutions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Municipalities within the Karditsa and Evrytania regions interested in promoting sustainable local development and tourism. b. Regional and national tourism boards looking to enhance and diversify their offerings. <p>Key Partners:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Local Government and Municipalities: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Municipality of Plastiras Lake b. Municipality of Mouzaki c. Municipality of Agrafa d. Regional authorities in Thessaly and Evrytania 2. Environmental and Conservation Organisations: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Local and regional NGOs focused on environmental protection and sustainable development. b. Organisations working on biodiversity conservation and natural resource management. 3. Cultural and Heritage Organisations: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Groups dedicated to preserving and promoting local cultural and historical heritage, including the maintenance of ancient trails and monasteries. 4. Tourism and Recreation Companies: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Local businesses and cooperatives involved in tourism, such as eco-tourism agencies, hiking and climbing clubs, and agri-tourism enterprises. 5. Educational Institutions and Research Bodies: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Universities and research centers studying environmental science, sustainable development, and cultural heritage. b. Schools and educational programs participating in environmental education and awareness campaigns.

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>6. Funding Bodies and Programmes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. National and European funding programs supporting sustainable development, environmental conservation, and community projects. b. Private investors and philanthropists interested in supporting eco-friendly initiatives and community empowerment.
Vision and Future plans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Construction, marking, and maintenance of hiking, climbing, and cycling routes. ● Providing services in alternative tourism, agritourism, ecotourism, and agri-food product promotion. ● Organizing events to promote sustainable development, human equality, and environmental protection. ● Participating in public activities to promote solidarity economy principles and collective/cooperative organisation. ● Creating or joining networks to support similar ventures and promote sustainable economic models. ● Offering training and certification in alternative tourism.

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2016 - 2019	Radio show 'Oxygono' on Palmos radio, Karditsa, focusing on nature and culture. Identified the missing gap of a “tool” for the development and implementation of actions that excite society. Initial planning, meetings, and research started this period.
2	2019	Official establishment of "Oxygen of Agrafa" as a Social Cooperative Enterprise.
3	2019	Established base in Neraida (mountains), initial equipment acquisition.
4	2020-2023	Maintenance, labeling, and network mapping trials in the Municipality of Limni Plastira (Karditsa). Trail formation and restoration in Anthochori, Municipality of Mouzaki (Karditsa). Cleaning of hiking trail Epiniana – Asprorema (Evritania).
5	2022	Submitted proposal for quality mark of Origin Plant Production Products in Thessaly.
6	2024	Planning creation of two Forest Schools in the Municipality of Limni Plastira. Exploring new ideas and seeking funding.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	Oxygen of Agrafa is highly local in terms of its resources. The cooperative utilises local knowledge and community involvement for the restoration and maintenance of trails. The natural environment and biodiversity of the Agrafa region are central to their activities, ensuring that inputs and resources are managed sustainably. Their focus on local tourism and environmental conservation directly benefits the surrounding community and preserves local natural resources.
team and network	5	The initiative boasts a strong and passionate team with a deep connection to the region. Many team members are experienced climbers and hikers, providing them with the necessary skills and knowledge. Additionally, Oxygen of Agrafa operates within a robust local ecosystem of stakeholders, including institutional and non-institutional entities, NGOs, and local communities, enhancing their interdisciplinary capabilities and support network.

effectiveness-relevance-applicability	4	Oxygen of Agrafa effectively addresses the problems it aims to solve, such as the degradation of natural trails and the need for sustainable tourism. Its activities are highly relevant, promoting environmental conservation and cultural heritage while fostering local tourism. The initiative is necessary as it provides significant benefits to society, the economy, and the environment by preserving trails, promoting local tourism, and engaging communities.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	4	The initiative included a research, experimentation, and piloting stage, which were crucial for its success. Oxygen of Agrafa has continued testing and refining its approaches. The model is realistically scalable and replicable in other rural areas of Europe, provided there is similar community involvement and environmental resources. The success in various municipalities demonstrates its potential for broader application.
financial sustainability	3	While Oxygen of Agrafa has multiple funding sources, including self-sustainability, contracts with public bodies, and national or European programs, detailed financial data would be needed to fully assess long-term sustainability. The reliance on various funding sources suggests a degree of financial stability, but continuous evaluation is necessary to ensure ongoing support and adaptability.
social cohesion	4	The initiative brings significant positive value to the community by involving locals in environmental conservation and promoting sustainable tourism. It fosters a sense of pride and ownership among community members, enhancing social cohesion. There is no indication of the initiative creating problems for the community; rather, it strengthens local ties and supports economic and social well-being.

Relevant links

1. <https://shorturl.at/jrALN>
2. <https://shorturl.at/aiDQ5> cleaning on the trail of the Asproremos Epiniana Evrytania
3. <https://shorturl.at/agtMX> from 00:18 to 02:40
4. <https://www.facebook.com/reel/737443615109302> reconstruction of a damaged path with the help of ropes (Agrafa region)
5. <https://www.facebook.com/100068526540714/videos/327014210049025> with a little help from my friends
6. <https://www.facebook.com/100068526540714/videos/976207800198389> The path in Asprorema was maintained and restored in a way that is also ideal for cyclists
7. <https://www.facebook.com/oxygenofm>

6.2.1.2 Conclusion

Oxygen of Agrafa successfully brings in a holistic approach to the sustainable development of anthropogenic activities while preserving the natural environment within which these activities take place, taking into account local microclimate and biodiversity. Specifically, this bio-based solution focuses on the restoration and maintenance of historical trails in the forests of Agrafa mountains and on the promotion of ecotourism, putting equal emphasis on the protection and empowerment of the environmental, cultural and social heritage of the region. Promoting participation and social cohesion of the local communities, via education and community building is at the heart of this Oxygen of Agrafa.

6.3 Bioeconomy Theme: Aquatic and Water Systems

6.3.1 The Fonda fish aquaculture

6.3.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	The Fonda fish aquaculture

General Information	
Subtitle - tagline	IMTA – Integrated Multi-Tropical Aquaculture
Bioeconomy theme	Aquatic
Core Activities	<p>FONDA is a private independent company that owns a marine aquaculture plant since 2003. Now it owns the only Slovene marine aquaculture plant for fish sea bass (<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>), sea bream (<i>Sparus aurata</i>) and shellfish - mussels (<i>Mytilus</i>) production. It has a unique approach to raising and selling its products. It developed a renowned brand Fonda Piran Sea Bass and Sea Bream, known for its superior quality.</p> <p>The company is also specialised in underwater and water-related work, e.g. design, planning of underwater structures, floating pontoons, surveys, sampling, photo and TV shootings, underwater search and rescue, and instruction of diving, underwater and hyperbaric techniques and technologies.</p> <p>FONDA's educational tourism program was awarded by the national Slovene tourism organisation with a Slovenia Unique Experience sign, for exceptional, innovative and authentic tourism products.</p>
Full Address	Liminjanska cesta 117, LUCIJA – LUCIA, 6320 Portorož – Portorose, Slovenia
No of employees	10-19
Funding sources	Fish farming, tourist tours, national and international projects

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	In addition to providing the highest quality cultivation system, Fonda are upgrading their breeding with the IMTA approach, dedicated to recycling the nutrients and substantially reducing pressure on the environment.
Detailed Description	Fonda has already adjoined bivalve cultivation, bivalves being the filtrators of organic material in a water column. They plan to add macroalgae cultivation - algae are known to recycle macro- and micronutrients by incorporating them into their biomass. This means that instead of polluting the environment, which can lead to massive die-off of marine organisms due to oxygen deprivation, nutrients are circulated through the trophic levels. Biomass can be used for many purposes: from fertilisers, soil amenders, biostimulants and biopesticides in agriculture, as feedstock for biofuels and bioplastics, and even to extract valuable compounds for cosmetics, phytopharmaceuticals or animal feed. The fish farm has also become a refuge for numerous fish and other marine organisms which is supported by the Fonda team.
The team behind the story	Fonda is a family company that employs 14 permanent staff and regularly collaborates with 4 consultants, of which 3 biologists and 3 professional divers. The staff, all lovers of the sea, are dedicated to maintaining and improving production of high-quality marine food, strict quality standards, sustainability and competitiveness.
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	The aquaculture plant is situated in the environmentally unique coastal area in the Gulf of Piran, Adriatic Sea, Slovenia, where it offers possibilities for economic development of the local community. Key clients are food and restaurant businesses, target audience all that are interested in healthy food and healthy sea, key partners are businesses but also educational institutions and governmental bodies.
Vision and Future plans	Further modernisation and optimisation of cost effectiveness and competitiveness of the whole aquaculture plant is planned, while efforts will be made for minimizing the impact of the plant on the surrounding environment. Environmental services will be promoted,

The Success Story Profile	
	including the action You(r)see, aimed at education, research and protection of the underwater world.

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	-	-

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	The aquaculture plant is situated in the environmentally unique coastal area in the Gulf of Piran, Adriatic Sea, Slovenia, where it offers possibilities for economic development of the local community. Fonda aquaculture is deeply involved with the local community, being the locals themselves, providing fish to stores and restaurants, educational tours of their aquaculture and being an important player in the Slovenian coastal area.
team and network	5	They are well connected with most relevant institutions that relate to their work, from universities, research companies to policy makers and restaurants/tourist agencies (https://www.fonda.si/en/fonda/partners). Irena Fonda has PhD in molecular biology, Lean Fonda is biologist and renown Slovene diver, underwater work planner and constructor.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	Marine fish farms with cages can have a profound impact on the environment, mostly through input of fish feces and uneaten feed that ends up in the sea. By adding other trophic level organisms that uptake the organic matter and macronutrients, the pressure on the environment can be greatly reduced. Fonda aquaculture has already a dedicated marine area for further upgrades as well as means of applying them.
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	4	Fonda aquaculture is supporting development and testing solutions on the pilot scale. Incorporation of macroalgae cultivation has been planned for several years with Algen, You(r)sea project is dedicated to support research and the IMTA system should be replicable in similar areas around the world. Similar IMTA systems in various environments are already becoming a welcome circular approach. Scalability is limited by the marine area limitation.
financial sustainability	5	Fish farming, tourist tours, national and international projects
social cohesion	5	Fonda cooperated with numerous local partners, locals and municipal bodies, contributing to the areas' economy and wellbeing.

Relevant links

1. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OFDBxE4h0b8>
2. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lkx73SboKP0>
3. [Feel Slovenia](#)
4. [Blue Schools for the Sea Oasis Piran - yoursea](#)

6.3.1.2 Conclusion

FONDA serves as a good paradigm in applying circular solutions in fish aquaculture to minimise environmental impact and achieve sustainability, through nutrient recycling systems and production of biomass that may be utilised in several bioeconomy applications. Research and innovation, via networking and collaborations with stakeholders and relevant organisations, together with a range of educational and engagement activities to inform and raise awareness regarding sustainable aquaculture systems are also factors that contribute to the success of this bio-based solution.

6.4 Bioeconomy Theme: Biomaterials and Bioproducts

6.4.1 Innovative Cellulose Products

6.4.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Innovative Cellulose Products
Subtitle - tagline	Paper and packaging solutions made from invasive plants or horticultural residues from the idea to the prototype
Bioeconomy theme	Biomaterials
Core Activities	Papermaking, Packaging solutions, Research & development, Laboratory and poly-industry testing, Consulting, Education
Full Address	Bogišičeva 8, 1000 Ljubljana, SL
No of employees	15
Funding sources	Self-sustainable, national funding, EU funding

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	<p>CiP is the trademark for Circular innovative papers made from discarded, residual or waste biomass. It is an opportunity for any local business/ municipality with their own biomass to create unique papers and/or packaging solutions with respect to sustainability and circularity principles.</p>
Detailed Description	<p>Residual biomass contains a valuable part of cellulose fibre.</p> <p>Our ideas were developed while solving the problem of the invasive plants' growth in the Municipality of Ljubljana. The biomass was tested for various characteristics – to obtain products with added value, including paper production. We have found that the characteristics (the proportion of cellulose) are suitable for the utilisation of the fibres for papermaking. At ICP we are intensively researching the potential of different types of lignocellulosic biomass. We also have our own database of different types of lignocellulosic biomass (chemical, mechanical and morphological properties). The database gives us basic information about the potential of each type of lignocellulosic biomass to produce different types of paper products.</p> <p>At ICP, we fractionate the fibres to produce paper or cardboard and design unique packaging that gives your products added visibility.</p> <p>We evaluate the economic and environmental impact of converting waste materials into products with added value for your own use or for the market. We design and produce selected products as office, printing or packaging paper/cardboard or unique paper packaging in small series.</p> <p>For your product or solution, we produce customised paper/ cardboard from interesting, locally available natural raw materials or even from waste biomass. Alternatively, you can also choose from our CiP papers in stock.</p> <p>With our in-depth technical knowledge and pilot production facilities, we can enrich your potential by producing prototypes and small series of final packaging solutions. Newly developed materials and finished products are also tested for compliance with market and legal requirements regarding food contact packaging and recyclability, biodegradability/compostability.</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>The sustainable and circular use of natural resources and manufacturers' commitment to quality, consumer safety and environmental protection are increasingly exposed requirements. With CiP papers made from locally collected, discarded biomass, we help you tell stories to your customers that set you apart from other suppliers. We offer papers with different weights, from 70 to 240 g/m² and in various formats up to B2. Our products are tested for offset, flexo and digital printing and are also suitable for all finishing processes. We offer comprehensive technical support and the creation of colour profiles for your printing processes. The papers are recyclable and safe to come into contact with food. They can be used for everything from fast food packaging to printing brochures, books, or calendars.</p> <p>Our modern and diverse equipment enables us to manufacture prototypes and small series of products tailored to the customer's needs.</p> <p>APPLAUSE project: Invasive alien plants (IAPs) represent a threat to local biodiversity and the ecosystem. On the other hand, IAPs rich in cellulose fibres are suitable for papermaking and innovative paper products that are environmentally friendly, biodegradable and compliant with the concept of a circular economy and zero waste green technology.</p>
The team behind the story	Experts from different interdisciplinary fields with many years of experience in the field of papermaking.
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>Target audience: Mostly B2B partners with their own biomass, that order specific products made from paper-like resources to end products. Some of the clients want to close their business model by allocating their side-streams into products they can use (i.e. packaging)</p> <p>Actual clients: Lušt, City of Ljubljana, Sadna pravljica, Pleterska hruška, Droga Kolinska</p> <p>Key partners: Pulp and paper institute (ICP)</p>
Vision and Future plans	ICP's vision is to become a leading, internationally recognised research and development institution, a reference laboratory for testing natural fibre and paper materials and products, and a regional research and training centre for the paper industry.

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2017-2020	Applause project https://www.ljubljana.si/sl/moja-ljubljana/applause/
2	2020-2022	<p>Lušt paper https://icp-lj.si/izdelane-vrecke-iz-nasega-papirja-iz-paradiznikovih-stebel/</p> <p>Paper bags 'Lušt-ne vrečke' https://icp-lj.si/srebrno-priznanje-tudi-za-icp/</p> <p>Corrugated cardboard from tomato stems https://icp-lj.si/prvic-v-zgodovini-icp-in-slovenije-valoviti-karton-iz-stebel-paradiznika/</p> <p>Patent https://icp-lj.si/patentiran-postopek-iz-delave-papirja-iz-odpadnih-stebel-paradiznika/</p>

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	Locally sourced and produced
team and network	5	Experts from different interdisciplinary fields with many years of experience in the field of papermaking.
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	5	100% recyclable, 100% compostable, food contact safe
Testing & piloting-scalability & replicability	4	Testing at the pilot level with the aim of development to the industrial level. There are only a few paper pilot plants in Europe. This is a definite advantage of our institute. We also have many clients outside of Slovenia.
financial sustainability	4	Production is in series (boutique), commercial sales are practically priced considering the products (special papers and products). Higher price that guarantees profit.
social cohesion	5	With our training (lectures, seminars, conferences ...) and cooperation with various educational institutions (excursions), we make a social cohesion.

Relevant links

1. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QwpKnt88fD4>
2. <https://icp-lj.si/?lang=en>

6.4.1.2 Conclusion

ICP provides a circular bio-based solution, to locally close the circle of waste and residual biomass and produce new products using secondary raw materials. This success story highlights the importance of both having good knowledge of the qualitative characteristics of the waste stream that is treated and conducting quality tests on products, in order to ensure that the final product will be suitable for the market - offering tailored solutions to their clients is another feature that makes products attractive and competitive. Moreover, the fact that a residual biomass producer may provide the raw material and receive new products for their needs raises awareness regarding the remaining value of waste and shifts minds towards the benefits of circular economy.

6.5 Bioeconomy Theme: Bioenergy

6.5.1 Energy Community of Karditsa

6.5.1.1 Success story report

General Information	
Success Story Title	Energy Community of Karditsa
Subtitle - tagline	
Bioeconomy theme	Bioenergy
Core Activities	Production of heating pellets from local biomass
Full Address	Agiopigi, Karditsa, Thessaly, Greece
No of employees	4
Funding sources	Members fees and EU Grants

The Success Story Profile	
Short description of bio-based solution	<p>The Energy Community of Karditsa (ESEK) is a citizen energy cooperative, established in 2010 to fulfill the vision and reward the efforts of its members. Its main purpose was to foster renewable energy in the region. In 2019, according to the provisions of national law 4513/2018 and following the unanimous decision of the General Assembly, the Energy Cooperative was converted into an Energy Community. Nowadays, it numbers more than 400 members, with an estimated 10% rate composed by municipalities, SMEs, associations etc. ESEK operates in Thessaly, an area with strong agricultural production. The continuous expansion of the local fossil fuel network threatens the uptake of RE heating solutions such as biomass boilers. At the same time, the region has a great biomass supply chain potential through agricultural, forestry and wood processing industries that can easily support the uptake of bioenergy technologies. The main activity of the Energy Community is related to the management of a biomass plant to produce solid biofuels for energy and heating (or cooling) purposes. The first phase of the investment project has accomplished an Energy Community with a solid biofuel plant which can set up the value chain for the local community.</p>
Detailed Description	<p>How it all started</p> <p>The Energy Service Cooperative of Karditsa (ESEK) was set up as an energy cooperative in the prefecture of Karditsa (Greece) in 2010. The group's objective was to promote the development of renewable energy sources in the region to the benefit of the wider community, building on the resources locally available. ESEK's thinking went beyond mere energy production – what the community wanted was to create a local value chain, from the people who produce the biomass to the people who consume the energy, with the purpose of strengthening the local economy as a priority.</p> <p>The project</p> <p>Solar PV was a consideration for the community's first project, however with the objective to create a local value chain, the community in 2013 decided to opt for residual biomass in the form of wood pellets. The prefecture of Karditsa is characterised by its mountains and significant agricultural activity. Both these elements provide residual biomass from agriculture and the forests. In addition, the region already had numerous processing industries in place. ESEK began to engage with biomass owners in the region, to highlight to them the potential for additional income and other benefits that could be obtained from a resource they already had in hand.</p>

The Success Story Profile	
	<p>At the time, the energy community numbered around 300 members, and was able to collect significant funds from them – approximately half of the budget needed for the plant. To close the financing gap, ESEK applied to the EU’s LEADER program, which financed the other half of the facility. The fundraising process started in 2015, the biomass plant was built in 2017. Today, the biomass plant produces 1 200 tonnes of pellets per year using agricultural, forest, wood processing and city pruning materials. If all of these pellets were used by households, this would cover the heating needs of about 250 households per year. In Karditsa, the pellets are used by households, farmers (i.e. to dry tobacco), municipal buildings, and industries. In addition to their biomass activities, ESEK submitted two applications for solar photovoltaic (PV) parks, one PV of 1MW and the second PV at the rooftop of the facilities about 100 KW in early 2023, aiming to establish several parks to address their electricity needs through collective self-consumption (CSC) via virtual net-metering. However, they currently face grid capacity limitations. The Distribution System Operator (DSO) has indicated that they must wait for grid expansion, which is currently paused due to financial constraints. In Greece, consumers can connect to the same CSC plant within the region irrespective of the distance in km.</p> <p>Their decision-making framework operates on the principles of “1 member, 1 vote”, with an Annual General Meeting (AGM) convened each year.</p>
The team behind the story	<p>A Group of motivated members consisting of Citizens, a cooperative bank, the chamber of commerce, the local development organisation, were the initiators that engaged the local stakeholders to become members and share a common vision about energy independence, valorisation of local resources, increase social cohesion and create new job opportunities.</p>
Target audience / Key client / Key partners	<p>The cooperative's journey began with a concerted effort to engage its members through numerous meetings, fostering awareness around the topic of community energy. These gatherings served as platforms for exchanging ideas and thoughts.</p> <p>ESEK has cultivated a strong relationship with the local municipality from the beginning and maintains ongoing communication with the grid operator regarding new solar projects. Key milestones in the community’s development and member engagement efforts included the joining of the local cooperative bank and the Chamber of Commerce. These two actors helped build confidence among other stakeholders, such as SMEs, local authorities, and non-governmental organisations to join the energy community. This in turn helped encourage local citizens’ trust in the undertaking.</p> <p>The cooperative prioritises its members, offering them preferential treatment as an incentive – for instance, when looking for a contractor, ESEK will first look within its member base. Recognizing the potential to boost income for local forest cooperatives and enable their continued presence in mountainous areas suffering from population loss due to urban centralisation, ESEK initiated conversations with these stakeholders to discuss a possible partnership. The residual biomass produced by Karditsa’s forests had previously not been used much – selling these elements now provides the forest cooperatives with additional income.</p> <p>The biofuel produced by the cooperative is made available to both its members and the wider community. Members enjoy a preferential pricing structure; the extent of the discount depends on factors like contribution and their specific needs. This difference in pricing can range from 15% to 20% among members, aligning with the cooperative's aim of promoting member benefits while supporting the community at large.</p>

The Success Story Profile	
Vision and Future plans	<p>As a next step, ESEK launched a co-creation process with its members aimed at expanding its biomass capacities to meet the electricity and heat demands of its members.</p> <p>One of their key collaborations in this endeavour is with the local municipality, which grapples with a challenge: each year, the municipality trims and prunes trees that leave behind a substantial amount of biomass as residue. The lack of processing facilities has led to the disposal of these residuals in illegal landfills – an issue many municipalities are struggling with - with many being incinerated, resulting in CO2 emissions and health problems. To address this issue, ESEK reached an agreement with the municipality to process part of the pruning residues in their biomass facility.</p> <p>In winter 2022, ESEK took their collaboration with the municipality a step further by becoming an Energy Service Company (ESCO). This led to a memorandum of cooperation, enabling the provision of residual biomass, including coffee waste, which was combined with wood to produce "coffee pellets". The addition of the coffee waste in the supply chain was implemented through a collaboration with incommon (a Greek NPO) and its project 'Kafsimo: recycling coffee waste'. These coffee pellets were used by the municipality to meet the heating needs of a local kindergarten, with ESEK installing the necessary boiler infrastructure. The use of this biofuel led to a significant reduction in fuel costs, approximately 24% less than traditional oil. The positive reception from both teachers and children has inspired ESEK to explore further installations of biomass boilers in additional municipal buildings. The cooperative is also dedicated to promoting the concept of circular (bio)economy.</p>

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
1	2010	ESTABLISHMENT OF KARDITSA ENERGY COOPERATIVE: An initiative of commercial chamber and agency development of Karditsa (AN.KA) that aligned with the hopes and ideas of several citizens of Karditsa. The simple idea of exploiting the local resources was enough to motivate more than 200 members to join.
2	2012	THE CREATION OF A SOLID BIOFUEL ENTERPRISE: On 23th of October 2012, the first step was decided. The creation of a pellet plant to process and standardise the residual biomass and create a local value chain in the region, reduce energy poverty and increase job creation.
3	2017	PELLET PRODUCTION: The use of European tools such as LEADER+ and the financial support of the cooperative bank of Karditsa set in motion the production of pellets. The community cooperates as a priority with its own members (technicians, engineers, biomass suppliers, fuel companies etc.), aiming to create a reliable and solid supply chain.
4	2019	2019 ENERGY COMMUNITY: The cooperative was transformed into an Energy Community in accordance with the provisions of Law 4513/2018. Since 2019 all six municipalities participate in the community and together plan the next steps regarding the exploitation of the local resources and renewables.
5	2022	THE ROLE OF AN ESCO: With the support of the European project BECoop, a new activity has been developed. A biomass boiler installed in a kindergarten and the community supply direct renewable heating. The municipality and the energy community intended to further install biomass boilers to municipal structures and reduce the carbon footprint of the municipality.

Milestones Timeline		
	Date / Year	Milestone
		FREE SOLAR PROJECT: A residential self-consumption installation can provide free energy from the sun that can reduce the energy bill by hundreds of euros annually. FREE SOLAR will allow consumers and small or medium-sized enterprises to self-finance the cost of their PV installation without any capital expenditure, based on savings generated by the PV installation once it is functional and generate free solar energy for over 25 years. ESEK's ambition is to provide solar energy to every Greek citizen and aid in the ongoing national struggle against the climate crisis, while contributing to the creation of a fair solar economy for all. The first pilot FREE SOLAR program has already been initiated in the Region of Thessaly and soon will expand to other regions of Greece.
6	2023	VIRTUAL NET METERING 1.2 MW: In January of 2023 an application was made for the creation of a PV park for the members of the community to cover their electricity demands through virtual net metering.
7	2024	Community of Renewable Energy: The community will transform into a Community Renewable Energy in accordance with the provisions of Law 5037/2023.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
local-ness	5	ESEK is completely based in the rural area of Karditsa, in mainland Greece. All the resources it requires come from local sources. It has in the past cooperated with local SMEs to provide for its needs in mechanical equipment, when possible. The majority of its products are also distributed locally.
team and network	4	<p>Citizens/Individual:</p> <p>364</p> <p>77.66 % men</p> <p>16.5 % women</p> <p>SMEs:</p> <p>20</p> <p>Municipalities:</p> <p>6</p> <p>Associations:</p> <p>10 (including cooperatives, chamber of commerce, agency of development of the municipality of Karditsa)</p>
effectiveness-relevance-applicability	4	It is empirically shown that Renewable Energy Cooperatives (RESCoops) are important enablers of the energy transition while also leading to various forms of social impact, including: increased acceptance of renewable energy developments (in contrast with commercially-led projects which are often faced with public opposition), faster uptake of low carbon technologies, more sustainable behaviours, and lower risk of energy poverty.

Key Indicator	Rating	Explanation
		In terms of applicability, the supply chain is resilient and renewable, the alternative is landfilling or other harmful disposal methods, and the need for energy and heating is inflexible. As such, the bio-based solution is both relevant and applicable to the area.
Testing & piloting- scalability & replicability	4	<p>Local resources, local stakeholders, local authorities. ESEK’s scheme utilises exclusively local resources, is addressed to local stakeholders, and involves local authorities to establish itself and expand its area of influence. This model is replicable in any rural area that can provide appropriate feedstock sources.</p> <p>Furthermore, ESEK has also taken part in the EU Horizon 2020 “BECoop”, during which there was performed a variety of activities related to expanding and securing a value chain of alternative feedstocks from the local community, formulating an optimal mix between them to produce high quality pellets and use them for community heating purposes. This scheme can be replicated in any rural area where there is a need for heating. It is also scalable, as it can utilise a wide variety of feedstocks to expand its production or expand to other areas of renewable energy (like photovoltaic).</p>
financial sustainability	3	<p>ESEK’s business plan requires the active participation of its members. It also requires a large initial investment, although this can be ameliorated by accessing European and state subsidies and funds for renewable energy endeavours. Since ESEK has already established itself in the local community, and developed bonds with various stakeholders and customers, as well as with the local municipality with which they have been working closely together (and plan to expand that cooperation in the near future by installing and managing more biomass boilers in various municipal buildings) it is sustainable financially. This is also compounded by the fact that it plans to expand its network of activities in other renewables in the near future (solar power), thus offering it a more diversified revenue stream.</p> <p>ESEK’s main hardship comes from the lack of cooperation with even more potential stakeholders, who are sceptical towards the various economic and social benefits it would offer them to cooperate with it, mostly due to lack of knowledge and awareness towards renewable energy. They offer a fair, standard market price so any aware consumer that means to support local businesses has no drawback to make the switch and support a strong, local, rural cooperative like ESEK.</p>
social cohesion	4	Community projects can provide flexibility and when connected to the main power system, increase the reliability and resilience of the whole system. They provide many socio – economic benefits in addition to low – cost renewable energy to the local community. Participation and action within energy communities also seems to strengthen social cohesion, as it enhances the dialogue between the members which share the benefits of RES, which is key to their long-term viability.

Relevant links

1. <https://www.esek.gr/>
2. <https://www.facebook.com/esekarditsas>
3. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dfTq3qVqXPg&ab_channel=ENERGYCOMMUNITYOFKARDITSA%28ESEK%29
4. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pWKP-iBSYwA&ab_channel=%CE%95%CE%B8%CE%BD%CE%B9%CE%BA%CF%8C%CE%91%CE%B3%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%84%CE%B9%CE%BA%CF%8C%CE%94%CE%AF%CE%BA%CF%84%CF%85%CE%BF
5. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eAPfDnCdWoA&t=197s&ab_channel=%CE%95%CE%A1%CE%A4%CE%91.%CE%95
6. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RNKIO7LKMx4&ab_channel=IEECP
7. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p-jORdEq33Y&ab_channel=EvangeloSipsas

6.5.1.2 Conclusion

Through ESEK's activities, renewable energy is produced via the utilisation of locally sourced residual biomass to cover the needs of ESEK's members and of the wider community, while local value chains are developed and empowered towards sustainability: circular management of resources, cleaner forms of energy, enabling and boosting regional development. The identification and assessment of local needs and opportunities to properly design and implement the relevant bio-based solutions, together with the establishment of a robust network of members and stakeholders, who are actively involved in the decision-making procedures, are some of the factors that contribute to the success of this endeavour. Finally, keeping up with policies and legislation is crucial to comply with and benefit from the relevant provisions.

7 Conclusions

Deliverable 2.6 was developed in the framework of Task 2.4: Identification of Success Stories in each Regional Bioeconomy Platform (RBP) and includes the first 20 bio-based solutions that were identified and selected as success stories across Europe. The report highlights the promising success stories within the rural bioeconomy across various regions of the European Union. By identifying and documenting these case studies, we have showcased the potential of bioeconomic activities to foster sustainable rural development, enhance local economies, and contribute to the EU's broader environmental and economic goals.

The number of success stories that have been identified per bioeconomy theme, i.e. food & agriculture, forestry, water & aquatic systems, biomaterials & bioproducts and bioenergy, is the following:

- 5 success stories related to “Food & Agriculture”
- 3 success stories related to “Forestry”
- 3 success stories related to “Water & aquatic systems”
- 6 success stories related to “Biomaterials & Bioproducts”
- 3 success stories related to “Bioenergy”.

Among these success stories, 19 have been uploaded to the BioRural Toolkit.

It is noted that, for the purposes of T2.4, at least 20 success stories in total, 5 per RBP covering all themes of the bioeconomy, i.e. 1 success story / bio-economy theme / RBP, need to be identified by the end of the Task (M36), while new success stories will be continuously invited to increase the pool of best practice examples.

The partnership is already close to meeting the KPI. Specifically, in the framework of D2.6 (M24), the partnership has already identified 20 success stories and 3 out of 4 RBP have already identified 1 success story / bio-economy theme. RBP leaders, together with their member-partners, are actively seeking for more success stories, while uncommon, as the task leader, continuously monitors the progress of the relevant activities and has planned accordingly, in order to complete the Task successfully. Additional success stories will be reported in Deliverable 2.7 Regional Bioeconomy Platform Success Stories Identification (1st update).